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Does climate finance improve the environmental quality of recipient countries? Evidence from shift share instrument

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Abstract

The effectiveness of climate finance in enhancing environmental outcomes remains an open question, particularly in developing and emerging economies. This paper investigates this question using panel data from 75 developing and emerging economies and instrumental variable approach. Our findings show that climate finance significantly improves environmental quality in recipient countries by reducing carbon emissions. These results are robust across multiple sensitivity checks including alternative measures of environmental quality¹. Local projection approach highlight a nonlinear dynamic effect, with the strongest impact occurring in the fourth year after disbursement and persisting until nine years. A heterogeneity analysis indicates that the effect is driven by mitigation finance. Moreover, Chinese climate finance exhibits a lower environmental impact than finance from DAC member countries. Regarding financial instruments, grants have a significant positive effect on environmental quality, whereas debt instruments do not. The benefits of climate finance are more pronounced in countries with higher innovation capacity, human capital, and lower debt burdens. We further explore the mechanisms through which climate finance operates. The analysis reveals that climate finance contributes to environmental improvements by accelerating the energy transition, increasing forest cover, reducing fossil fuel consumption, and improving the energy efficiency of GDP. Using disbursed rather than committed finance data strengthens the effect, and we find that climate finance has a much stronger effect than general foreign aid. These results offer policy-relevant insights into how climate finance can be better targeted and structured to enhance environmental outcomes in developing countries.

Keywords: Climate Finance, Carbon Footprint, Carbon Intensity, Ecological Footprint, Shift-Share Instrument, Local Projection.

JEL Classification: F37, O44, Q54, Q53, C26, C32

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1. Ecological Footprint, Carbon Intensity of GDP, and Environmental Performance Index (EPI).

1 Introduction

The concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere has caused unprecedented global warming, resulting in significant damage to human societies and natural ecosystems. The number of climate-related natural disasters recorded between 1900 and April 2024 stands at approximately 26,000, associated with over 20 million human casualties and \$130 trillion in economic losses (Lee et al., 2022; EM-DAT, 2024). In addition to these alarming statistics, the 2023 report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) indicates an acceleration of global warming for the coming years, with temperatures projected to exceed the Paris Agreement target of 1.5°C as early as 2030, under business as usual scenario (Lee et al., 2023). Achieving the ambitious goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C and 2°C will therefore only be possible by accelerating and intensifying pollution reduction efforts to reach a peak in CO₂ emissions by 2030 (requiring a global reduction of 43% by 2030 compared to 2019) (Lee et al., 2023). These statistics highlight the urgent need to address climate change and emphasize the importance of enhancing efforts to mitigate global warming involving a substantial decrease in greenhouse gas emissions, which are the main contributing factor.

The various agreements reached within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) pursue this objective through the implementation of various climate and environmental policies such as national and regional carbon trade systems, Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), and REDD+² mechanisms. Adopted in 2015 and entered into force in 2016, the Paris Agreement also introduces National Determined Contributions (NDCs) as its compliance mechanism. This approach depends on NDCs submitted by participating countries to reduce global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Climate finance initiated after the Kyoto Protocol by industrialized countries through the establishment of fast-start funds³ is also seen as an effective solution to combat climate change by promoting clean production systems and now occupies a central role in climate agreement negotiations (Carfora et al., 2017; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Bhandary et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022). Indeed, in order to promote equity in addressing climate change, the UNFCCC issued a recommendation subsequent to the Kyoto Protocol, urging developed nations to assist developing countries in implementing their adaptation and mitigation strategies. This call stems from the historical responsibility attributed to developed countries for contributing to global warming. Moreover, this financial support holds significant importance for climate-related initiatives in developing nations, given their elevated vulnerability to climate change impacts and their limited resources that expose them to a continual trade-off between preserving environmental quality and pursuing economic development objectives (Espagne, 2016; Lee et al., 2022; Zhang and Pan, 2016; Mehrotra and Benjamin, 2022). This financial commitment was renewed in the Paris Agreement, with developed countries aiming to reach a floor level of \$100 billion in climate funds by 2020. This target was not achieved by the specified date (Pauw et al., 2022; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022) and the new collective quantified goal on climate finance, set at USD 300 billion per year by 2035 falls short of the estimated needs, which are projected to reach USD 600 billion annually in the national determined contribution (CPI, 2024; Isah et al., 2025).

As mentioned by the UNFCCC, climate finance broadly refers to local, national or transnational financing drawn from public, private and alternative sources of funding seeking to support mitigation and adaptation actions. In line with this

2. REDD+: Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation. Thanks to REDD+, many countries are taking concrete actions to protect their forests. By the end of 2022, REDD+ activities implemented by developing countries cover a forest area of about 1.37 billion hectares (approximately 62% of the forest area of developing countries) and about 75% of global deforestation (United Nations, 2023)

3. Under the 2009 Copenhagen Accord, developed countries collectively committed to mobilize climate action funds worth \$100 billion annually by 2020 to assist developing countries in producing low-carbon technologies and engaging in climate change-resilient development actions. They pledged at this conference to mobilize \$30 billion USD between 2010 and 2012 to support climate action, and these funds are known as fast-start funds (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022).

objective, the question of the environmental effectiveness of these funds arises in economic literature. Although literature on climate finance is relatively recent, a number of studies have addressed climate funds. Topics covered include the determinants of demand and allocation of climate financing (Zhang and Pan, 2016; Pickering et al., 2017; Robinson and Dornan, 2017; Saunders, 2019; Mehrotra and Benjamin, 2022), the equity of the global response to climate change and climate finance conditionality (Winkler and Dubash, 2016; Betzold and Weiler, 2017; Dafermos, 2025), the climate finance gap and climate finance policies taxonomy (Bhandary et al., 2021; Pauw et al., 2022; CPI, 2023, 2024; Isah et al., 2025), and their environmental performance (Carfora et al., 2017; Boly, 2018; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Bhandary et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022; Zoungrana et al., 2024; Miao et al., 2024). By using various econometric methods and data sources, certain studies offer empirical support for the effectiveness of climate funds in improving environmental quality by notably decreasing greenhouse gas emissions at both the national and firm levels (Carfora et al., 2017; Boly, 2018; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021; Miao et al., 2024; Zoungrana et al., 2024). Conversely, other research indicates that climate funds do not impact environmental quality (Kang and Jung, 2016; Li et al., 2021; Mahalik et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). For those finding a positive effect of climate funds on environmental quality, some of them highlight that this effect varies depending on the type of financing (multilateral, bilateral, adaptation, mitigation), the type of countries (developing island countries), and other factors such as financial development, economic development and donors characteristics (Boly, 2018; Carfora et al., 2017; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2021). Some of these analyses also show that climate finance promotes energy transition by increasing the consumption of renewable energy or reducing fossil energy consumption (Zhao et al., 2013; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022).

This emerging literature addresses relevant aspects on climate finance but presents methodological limitations regarding the issue of endogeneity, particularly for studies assessing the effects of climate funds on the environmental quality. Indeed, several factors contribute to the potential endogeneity in the relationship between environmental quality and climate funds. Firstly, the literature on climate finance allocation emphasizes that physical characteristics such as vulnerability to extreme weather events, endowment of carbon sinks such as forests, and emission levels can influence both the frequency and volumes of aid received for the climate change mitigation and adaptation (Robinson and Dornan, 2017; Carfora et al., 2017; Boly, 2018; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Saunders, 2019). Second, beyond physical characteristics, a self-selection phenomenon may be observed in the allocation of climate funds. Developing countries are competing for aid and are inclined to formulate environmental policies to attract more climate funds. Beside this, climate aid conditionality from donors may introduce endogeneity into this relationship. In order to ensure the efficacy of their financing, some donor countries may condition their funding on the environmental efforts of recipient countries. Finally, as environmental quality is a global public good that deal with transboundary externalities, climate finance may target countries with high CO₂ emissions to reduce long-term global warming. Carfora et al. (2017) support this hypothesis by showing that major polluters like China⁴ and India are among the recipients of more climate funds.

Some of the studies mentioned above have attempted to address endogeneity of climate finance by using Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) (Boly, 2018; Lee et al., 2022; Zoungrana et al., 2024) and propensity score matching (PSM) methods (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019), but the results remain inconclusive due to the small number of observations, which could affect the quality of matching⁵ in a macro framework, and the non-accounting for unobservable characteristics. For

4. For example, in 2022, China accounted for 31% of global emissions and 42% of global climate finance (CPI, 2024).

5. This study use a dataset including countries that have received funds in 2010(treated – 83 countries) and those that did not receive funds (untreated –66 countries).The fact that the treated countries are superior to the control affects the quality of the matching because several countries could be matched to the same control. Additionally, PSM (Propensity Score Matching) does not account for unobservables that may influence the estimation results.

GMM method, results can be highly sensitive to misspecification. Additionally, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the channels through which climate funds affect emissions. There is also a lack of evidence on the likely heterogeneity of results depending on the financial instruments used for climate aid allocation (debt vs. subsidy). In addition, existing analyses fail to consider the financial, social and innovation preconditions, necessary for improving the effectiveness of climate funds. Moreover, to our knowledge, there is no empirical research examining the role of Chinese climate finance in supporting emissions mitigation, despite the growing scale of such aid in recent years (Horn et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024a)⁶. Finally, the existing literature fails to identify a clear and robust trajectory of the dynamic effects of climate finance on emissions over time, often relying on GMM methods (Boly, 2018; Lee et al., 2022; Zougrana et al., 2024) that account for the persistence of environmental outcomes but not for the dynamic effects of climate finance itself (Kruiniger, 2009).

Our study aims to fill this gap by four main contributions. First, to address endogeneity concerns in the climate funds and the environmental performance relationship we use a new composite instrument following the analytical framework of Borusyak et al. (2022). To our knowledge, this study is the first in the climate finance literature to use the shift-share instrument design to tackle the endogeneity of climate finance flows. What makes this approach special is that it combines shocks experienced by donor countries with how those shocks are shared across recipient countries. This allows us to take into account the characteristics of all parties involved in the bilateral allocation of climate funds, making our impact estimates more reliable and meaningful. Second, we undertake a series of novel heterogeneity analyses that significantly advance the existing literature. In particular, we explore how the effects vary according to the types of financial instruments used in allocating climate funds, the debt burden faced by recipient countries, their levels of human capital, and their technological innovation efforts. These insights offer nuanced and actionable policy guidance, helping policymakers to tailor climate finance strategies to diverse country contexts for greater effectiveness. Third, we offer a new way to analyze how the effects of climate finance evolve over time. Most existing studies rely on GMM methods, but these can fall short when the impact of climate finance is persistent. In such situations, the internal instruments used in GMM become weak, which can lead to biased results (Kruiniger, 2009). Also, GMM does not allow us to clearly show how the effect changes from year to year, making it hard to understand the real dynamic of climate finance. We use the local projection method combined with our IV approach, to illustrate the dynamic and robust effect of climate finance over time. Finally, we extend the scope of climate finance analysis beyond traditional DAC members by exploring the role of non-DAC donors, with a particular focus on China. While most existing studies concentrate on climate finance from DAC countries, we highlight the growing importance of emerging donors in the international climate finance landscape. Given China's increasing presence in global financial flows (Horn et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024a), we investigate the impact of Chinese climate-related funding on the environmental performance of recipient countries, drawing on data from GODAD (Bomprezzi et al., 2024).

Our results show that climate funds serve as a source of environmental quality improvement in recipient countries. A 1% increase in climate finance reduces carbon footprint by 0.051% for commitments finance and 0.087% for disbursed financing. This finding remains robust across a range of robustness tests, including alternative measure of environmental quality variables and alternatives instrumental variables, additional control variables, exclusion of BRICS countries, winsorization and local projection method. Total aid estimations suggests that the effect is specific to climate related aid as ODA effect is lower than climate relative finance. Chinese climate aid has a weaker effect on carbon emissions compared to climate finance

6. Wang et al. (2024a) evaluate the effect of Chinese overall foreign aid on greenhouse gas emissions in a sample of 118 countries from 2000 to 2018. They find that Chinese foreign aid increased the overall carbon emission levels of recipient countries during the sample period, with each 1% increase in Chinese foreign aid being associated with a 0.0148% increase in the carbon emissions of recipient countries.

from DAC member countries. Energy transition, energy efficiency and reforestation constitute the primary transmission channel for these effects. Heterogeneity analysis reveals that finance provided through subsidies significantly reduces carbon footprint, while debt instrument has no significant effect. Mitigation funds also have a significant effect on carbon footprint, whereas the effect of adaptation funds is found to be non-significant. Multilateral financing also exhibits a non-significant effect in our case. Countries with high innovation capacity and low debt burden exhibit significant effects, whereas the effect proves to be non-significant for those with low innovation capacity and smaller in those with high debt burden. Furthermore, our results reveal that the level of education significantly impacts the effectiveness of climate funds. In countries with high levels of primary, secondary, and tertiary education, the effect of climate finance is significant, whereas it lacks significance in countries with lower levels of education. Within nations with higher education standards, the influence of climate funds is notably strong for countries with advanced education levels, particularly within tertiary education.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section presents stylized facts on climate finance, Section 3 briefly reviews the literature on the effectiveness of climate funds, Section 4 outlines our identification strategy and the data used for this analysis. Section 5 presents and discuss our empirical results including the baseline results, the robustness and heterogeneity analysis as well as the results of transmission channels and the final section concludes.

2 Climate finance: what does the data tell us ?

The graph presented below depicts a rising trajectory in both climate finance and carbon footprint among the countries examined in our study from 2000 to 2020. Notably, the surge in climate finance became more pronounced around the 2010s, potentially driven by the implementation of fast-start funds subsequent to the recommendations made during the 15th Conference of the Parties (COP15) convened in December 2009 in Copenhagen (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019). We can also observe that the increase in climate finance is primarily driven by mitigation funds, which show a nearly similar trend to the total climate finance until the end of the 2000s decade. This predominance of mitigation funds could be attributed not only to donors' willingness to provide mitigation financing but also to the fact that the OECD data source only records adaptation financing from 2009 onward. An analysis of the distribution of bilateral financing by financial instrument reveals that a significant portion of funds is provided to developing countries through the subsidy instrument (see figure 12 in appendix). This provides a favorable argument for our heterogeneity analysis by financial instrument conducted in the empirical part. Sectoral distribution indicates that the energy sector are one of the largest recipients of climate funds, accounting for approximately 10% of total financing, trailing behind the agriculture and forestry sector and the environmental protection sector (see figure 11 in appendix). This forms the foundation for our examination of transmission channels within these sectors.

Concerning the allocation of climate funds, figures 6 to 9 in appendix and table 1 predominantly illustrate that climate funds are directed towards countries with the highest greenhouse gas emissions. This observation supports our hypothesis that donor countries pursue a goal of preserving the global public good by allocating their climate aid where emissions are highest. As for adaptation funds, which are intended to go to the most vulnerable countries according to the literature, a comparison of Figures 6 and 8 in appendix and table 1 reveals the opposite as the correlation is non significant. African countries, which are among the most vulnerable, receive less funding compared to Asian and Eastern European countries, which are relatively less vulnerable. These findings are consistent with those of Saunders (2019), who highlights that the allocation of adaptation funding does not consistently align with the principles of the Paris Agreement. This agreement advocates for

financial resources to be provided to support developing countries, with a focus on nations particularly susceptible to the negative impacts of climate change.

Given China’s growing role in international finance in general and in development assistance in particular over recent decades (Horn et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024a), and the fact that its financial flows are not included in the main dataset used for this analysis, we rely on the geocoded Chinese aid database (GODAD⁷) to understand how its climate-related funding influences environmental outcomes in recipient countries. We filter the data to retain only projects with environmental objectives, based on the selection criteria used by the OECD (Rio markers). The figure below shows a modest increase in Chinese climate finance over the study period. Furthermore, Figure 13 highlights the relatively small share of Chinese climate-related funds compared to those from DAC donors, accounting for only 4.6% of the total in our sample.

Table 1 – Correlation between climate finance, carbon Footprint and vulnerability

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Climate Finance (1)	1.0000				
Mitigation Finance (2)	0.9664*	1.0000			
Adaptation Finance (3)	0.7284*	0.5432*	1.0000		
Carbon Footprint (4)	0.2558*	0.2789*	0.1323*	1.0000	
Vulnerability (5)	0.0276	0.0080	0.0574	-0.1260*	1.0000

Figure 1 – Evolution of climate finance and carbon footprint over 2000-2020 period

Source: Author Calculation from OECD and EORA data.

7. The Geocoded Official Development Assistance Dataset (GODAD) provides access to a broad range of geocoded Official Development Assistance and other development finance data. This Dataset includes 18 European donors (1973-2020), the United States (1973-2020), the World Bank (1995-2023), India (2007-2014), and China (2000-2021) (Bomprezzi et al., 2024).

3 Literature Review

In recent years, climate finance has become a key subject of discussion in academic and policy literature. Over time, it has become a crucial aspect in the various rounds of negotiations for climate agreements, involving both developing and developed countries (Espagne, 2016; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Bhandary et al., 2021). The literature addresses various aspects of climate finance, including the climate finance gap to achieve the objective of the Paris agreement (Pauw et al., 2022; Mehrotra and Benjamin, 2022; Lee et al., 2023; CPI, 2023, 2024), the determinants of demand and allocation of climate funds (Zhang and Pan, 2016; Carfora et al., 2017; Pickering et al., 2017; Robinson and Dornan, 2017; Boly, 2018; Saunders, 2019), the fairness of global responses to climate change and climate finance conditionality, and the effectiveness of climate finance allocation (Winkler and Dubash, 2016; Betzold and Weiler, 2017; Dafermos, 2025), as well as the impact of climate finance on environmental outcomes (Kang and Jung, 2016; Carfora et al., 2017; Boly, 2018; Wang et al., 2019; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Wu et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Mahalik et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022; Wang et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2023; Miao et al., 2024; Zoungrana et al., 2024).

We focus our review on the impact of climate finance on environmental quality, exploring both macroeconomic and firm-level studies and taking into account the adaptation and mitigation funds effect. Indeed, combating climate change is both a challenge and an opportunity to promote environmental quality and low-carbon development pathways simultaneously, especially for developing countries that generally lack the financial support and technology to cope with climate change and ecological degradation (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Mehrotra and Benjamin, 2022; Lee et al., 2022; Dafermos, 2025). Climate finance serves then as a crucial funding source that helps mitigate the ongoing trade-off in developing countries between preserving environmental quality, which is a global public good, and addressing national challenges to improve living conditions (Espagne, 2016; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022). As an international tool to fight against climate change, climate finance plays a crucial role in the adaptation and mitigation efforts of developing countries. Numerous studies have demonstrated that climate finance contributes to achieve a transition to an environmentally sustainable world by transforming the energy structure and attaining net-zero emissions (Zhao et al., 2013; Zhang and Pan, 2016; Carfora et al., 2017; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022; Zoungrana et al., 2024; Miao et al., 2024). A substantial portion of adaptation research is concentrated on the Pacific, independent island states, and the central regions of Small Island Developing States (SIDS). This body of research highlights a diverse array of adaptation strategies employed in SIDS, encompassing structural, physical, and behavioral change (Klöck and Nunn, 2019). Regarding studies that assess the mitigation impact of climate funds, Carfora and Scandurra (2019) use propensity score matching (PSM) analysis to study the impact of climate funds dedicated to renewable energy generation and biosphere protection. They find that countries which received 'fast-start' climate funds in 2010 experienced reductions in GHG emissions and made a greater shift towards renewable energy sources. By focusing on multilateral financing, Lee et al. (2022) also show significant negative effect of climate finance on carbon dioxide emissions of recipient developing countries. Moreover, the heterogeneity analysis conducted reveals that Small Island Developing States (SIDS) are more effective in utilizing climate finance to reduce carbon dioxide emissions and transition towards a low-carbon pathway. In addition, the impact of climate finance on carbon dioxide emissions is more pronounced in countries that have higher economic development and lower financial development. This result is explained by the fact that less economically developed countries may face challenges such as limited technological capabilities, weaker institutional frameworks, and less existing infrastructure. It also suggest that financial development would facilitate the mobility of brown capital, which in turn reduces the effectiveness of climate funds (Lee et al., 2022).

Other papers also show that climate finance strengthen the environmental quality by reducing both carbon emission and ecological footprint (Zougrana et al., 2024; Miao et al., 2024).

Additional research shows that climate funds support the transition to renewable energy and help in the reforestation efforts (Carfora et al., 2017; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022). A 1% increase in climate funds leads to a rise in renewable energy consumption and generation ranging from 0.05% to 19% (Carfora et al., 2017; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022). Carfora and Scandurra (2019) and Wu et al. (2021) also emphasize a significant impact of climate finance on fossil fuels. They note that a 1% increase in climate finance leads to a reduction in fossil fuel usage ranging from 0.12% to 17%. Contrary to previous analyses, some researchers argue that climate-related development assistance does not significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Kang and Jung, 2016; Li et al., 2021; Mahalik et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022). They point out that conditionally financing climate mitigation is ineffective in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, emphasizing the relative importance of general or unconditional development financing. Some of these analyses indicate a nonlinear effect of climate finance by showing that higher amounts of climate aid tend to increase the CO₂ emissions of recipient countries (Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022). This suggests that the conditionality of climate funds could hinder their effectiveness and emphasizes the importance for donor countries to align their assistance with the overall mitigation strategy of recipient countries in order to make it more impactful.

Some case studies at the firm level have found that green finance can significantly lower a company's carbon intensity. This reduction is achieved by decreasing the carbon intensity of investments and enhancing the environmental oversight of projects. On average, companies receiving green credits see a reduction in carbon intensity of 0.17 tons per 100 yuan compared to those that do not receive these credits (Xu et al., 2023).

Although the existing literature on climate finance seems extensive, there are still important aspects that require further exploration. Firstly, there is insufficient analysis regarding the endogeneity of climate funds, which is crucial for a more accurate assessment of their impacts. Secondly, considering the political economy surrounding the debate on climate fund efficiency, it is advisable to direct the analysis toward economic policy issues. This should involve accounting for the varied debt burdens among countries, the technological innovation capacity, and evaluating the effectiveness of the different financial instruments used to allocate climate funds to developing countries. Moreover, the dynamic impact of climate finance on environmental quality remains insufficiently explored in the literature with robust method. Consistent with this, we hypothesize that climate finance enhances the environmental quality of developing countries by significantly reducing their carbon footprint. The main mechanisms through which climate finance improves environmental quality are the transition to clean energy, the improvement of energy efficiency of production, and reforestation. We also propose that the impact of climate funds on reducing carbon emissions varies depending on the financial instrument used to allocate these funds, the innovation effort of recipient countries, and that debt burden may diminish the environmental effectiveness of climate finance. We additionally propose that the impact of climate finance on environmental quality is influenced by the recipient countries' level of human capital.

4 Data and Methodology

4.1 Data description

To conduct our empirical analysis, we combine data from multiple sources covering a sample of 75 developing recipient countries over the period from 2000 to 2020, leading to a total of 1,575 observations for the econometric estimation at the recipient level

We focus on developing countries for several reasons. Firstly, developing countries are still in the early stages of development, and their future progress will likely be associated with environmental degradation under a business as usual scenario (Lee et al., 2022). Second, unlike developed nations, developing countries have made less progress in terms of financial development and technology to address climate change and environmental degradation (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022). Third, given the trade-off that developing countries currently experience between environmental protection social and goals, climate finance serves as a mechanism to alleviate budget constraints. This provides these nations with the opportunity to pursue low-carbon development pathways (Espagne, 2016; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Lee et al., 2022).

4.1.1 Dependent variables

To estimate our econometric specification, we alternatively use four dependent variables as measures of the environmental quality of recipient countries. Carbon footprint per capita is used as the main dependent variable for our analysis. We also use ecological footprint per capita, carbon intensity of GDP and environmental performance index in our robustness analysis. The carbon footprint and carbon intensity of GDP come from the EORA database, which estimates CO₂ emissions based on consumption-based accounting, taking into account national CO₂ emissions augmented by those related to trade and estimated from a bilateral trade matrix. They are measured respectively in gigatonnes of equivalent CO₂ (GgCO₂eq) and gigatonnes of CO₂ equivalent per billion dollar of GDP (GgCO₂eqPerBnUSDGDP). The ecological footprint comes from the Global Footprint Network and measures the area of land needed for an individual or population to meet its needs. It is expressed in global hectares (gha), which represents the capacity of land to produce resources and absorb waste for a given population. Regarding the Environmental Performance Index (EPI), it is a synthetic measure of sustainability constructed using 58 performance indicators divided into 11 environmental issues categories. The final index represents a weighted average of these 58 indicators and ranges from 0 to 100. A high index indicates that the country has strong environmental policies. The EPI⁸ is developed by the Center for Environmental Law and Policy of Yale University. As a major source of greenhouse gas, carbon dioxide emissions can capture environmental degradation due to anthropogenic activities related to economic growth. Then it is used extensively to proxy environmental quality in the literature, as it is one of the most important drivers of environmental degradation (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Chen and Lee, 2020; Lee et al., 2022). The ecological footprint can also be used as an indicator of environmental degradation, as it measures human pressure on resources and ecosystems by comparing resource demand to the planet’s biocapacity (GFN, 2019). The Global Ecological Network illustrates that Earth’s “overshoot day” occurs earlier every year. By August 1, 2024, humanity had already depleted all the resources that the planet can renew within a year. This increasingly highlights the growing pressure of human activities on the environment, making this indicator suitable for measuring environmental quality. Some empirical studies like Alola et al. (2022) and Xue

8. There are other indicators focused on the stringency of environmental policies, but this one is only available for OECD countries (Kruse et al., 2022).

et al. (2021) have already employed this indicator to analyze, respectively, the dynamics of China’s ecological footprint and the effect of renewable energy use on the ecological footprint of four Asian countries⁹. Given that climate finance seeks to promote sustainable development, carbon intensity of GDP also serves as a valuable metric for assessing the environmental efficacy of climate funds. Following our baseline specification below, we consider the logarithm of these various variables in our econometric analysis.

4.1.2 Climate Finance

For climate finance data, we rely on climate-related development finance records from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the Geocoded Official Development Assistance Dataset (GODAD). These are project-level datasets that we filtered and aggregated to construct country-level indicators. The OECD dataset includes climate-related development finance from bilateral, multilateral and private philanthropic sources including both concessional and non-concessional activities. Guarantees are excluded because they are categorised as non-flow operations. We reprocess the database to reconstruct new climate fund variables by distinguishing between bilateral and multilateral financing, funding provided through debt channels, and that granted through subsidies. These data are provided in 2021 thousand dollars, and we consider the logarithm of the GDP ratio of the various climate fund variables to align with our baseline model below. Given that this database provides data on climate finance commitments, we consider disbursement data from the Credit Reporting System (CRS), which unfortunately has a time lag as it is reported starting from 2002. So we use this variable in the robustness test but not for the entire analysis. For the GODAD dataset, we filter the data to retain only projects with environmental objectives, based on the selection criteria used by the OECD (Rio markers). While the OECD dataset covers the period from 2000 to 2022 and the GODAD dataset spans from 2000 to 2021, we restrict our analysis to the period up to 2020 to minimize the rate of missing values for some of our control variables¹⁰

4.1.3 Control Variables

To accurately measure the effect of climate finance on environmental quality, we control for a set of variables whose impact on countries environmental quality has been evidenced in the literature. These variables can be categorized into three main groups: socioeconomic indicators, demographic indicators, and governance indicators. On the socioeconomic side, we use the green Solow model developed by Brock and Taylor (2010) as a framework to identify the main determinants of environmental quality. Building on this model and according to the previews studies, we incorporate population growth, and investment as control variables (Lee et al., 2022). We consider both public and private investment in our estimates to better understand their impact on carbon footprint. The importance of population size in relation to environmental quality is well-documented in various studies (Carfora et al., 2017; Boly, 2018; Su; Lee et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2022). Some researchers contend that a larger population degrades environmental quality through heightened energy use and increased carbon emissions (Su; Lee et al., 2022; Carfora et al., 2017) while others suggest that a growing population may foster urbanization, which can enhance infrastructure development. This development leads to more efficient public facilities and industrial concentration, thereby potentially reducing energy consumption and lowering emissions (Guo et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022).

9. Other studies have also used the ecological footprint as an indicator of environmental quality (Ulucak and Lin, 2017; Destek and Sinha, 2020; Zoungrana et al., 2024; Miao et al., 2024)

10. Other more comprehensive sources of climate finance data, such as those from the Climate Policy Initiative, could have been used for our analysis, but their temporal coverage is limited. Moreover, these data are not publicly available (CPI, 2024)

Beyond these indicators, additional control variables could be included in our model according to previous studies. These variables refer to outcomes of policies that do not directly aim at environmental conservation but are documented in the literature to influence environmental performance. Specifically, economic growth is believed to induce structural transformations within nations, which can affect their carbon emissions. Although economic growth may initially lead to an increase in CO₂ emissions, it often also triggers a transition to activities that are less carbon-intensive. Consequently, the overall impact of economic growth on emissions is not straightforward and cannot be determined without empirical analysis (Combes et al., 2016). To take this into account, we include the GDP per capita logarithmic value to account for outliers. By following Lee et al. (2022), we also control for industry value added, foreign direct investment, and energy intensity. We include industry value added because industrialization is generally associated with increased carbon emissions (Li and Lin, 2015; Lee et al., 2022). We also include energy intensity in our analysis because countries that rely heavily on energy-intensive sources typically depend on fossil fuels to propel their economic development. This reliance complicates efforts to implement renewable energy investments within climate finance frameworks (Lee et al., 2022). Beyond energy intensity, we incorporate variables such as access to electricity, renewable energy consumption, and fossil fuel consumption in our analysis. We use renewable energy, fossil fuel consumption and energy efficiency of GDP to explore the mechanisms through which our core results operate. Additionally, to account for technological spillovers from other investment sources, we also consider foreign direct investment (FDI). FDI is included to capture the potential effects of technology transfer, as developing countries often rely on external support to implement expensive mitigation policies that aim to tackle climate change, and safeguard the environment (Su et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022). We also include trade openness to control for potential sources of emissions originating from economic partners, although the effects of trade on emissions remain ambiguous (Antweiler et al., 2001).

Political economy models also theoretically suggest that higher income inequality contributes to increased environmental degradation (Borghesi et al., 2006; Ravallion et al., 2000; Berthe and Elie, 2015; Hu et al., 2021). Two main factors explain the channel through which inequalities affect environmental quality: the first relates to aggregate environmental degradation driven by individuals' economic behavior, and the second concerns the implementation of public policies aimed at environmental protection (Berthe and Elie, 2015). Ravallion et al. (2000) assert that the effect of income inequality on environmental degradation depends on the marginal propensity to emit (MPE). They argue that if the poor exhibit a higher MPE than the rich, decreasing income inequality could lead to an increase in pollution. Recent studies have also shown that corruption has not only a moderating effect on the relationship between income inequality and carbon emissions (Wang et al., 2024b) but also reduce countries ability to innovate their production process; thus exposing them to the use of carbon intensive production systems (Wen et al., 2023). To consider these influences, we have introduced the corruption index and the Gini index as additional variables in our analysis. The share of the female population in parliament is also included in our analysis because research indicates that women tend to have stronger preferences for environmental protection and related issues (Zhao et al., 2013; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019). Consequently, this variable serves as a proxy for the population's inclination towards greener policy management. It acts as an indicator of 'green sentiment' and reflects the public's attitude towards the use of climate funds (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019). For measurements of various indicators and the source of the data, see Table 16 in the appendix for more details.

4.2 Methodology

The identification strategy used in this analysis falls within the general framework of instrumental variables. Indeed, we hypothesize that the environmental quality of recipient countries may affect the level and the frequency of climate finance they receive. Several factors contribute to the potential endogeneity in the relationship between environmental quality and climate funds. Firstly, the literature on climate finance allocation emphasizes that the physical characteristics such as vulnerability to extreme weather events, carbon sink endowment such as forests, and emission levels, can influence both the frequency and volumes of aid received for climate change mitigation (Carfora et al., 2017; Robinson and Dornan, 2017; Boly, 2018; Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Saunders, 2019). Second, climate finance may be subject to a self-selection phenomenon. Indeed, developing countries are competing for aid and are inclined to formulate environmental policies to attract more climate funds. Beside this, climate aid conditionality from donors may introduce endogeneity into this relationship. In order to ensure the efficacy of their financing, some donor countries may condition their funding on the environmental efforts of recipient countries and grant more aid to environmental reform-oriented government. For example, the Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST)¹¹ of the International Monetary Fund mandates a series of economic and environmental reforms as prerequisites for funding access (IFM, 2024). Finally, as environmental quality is a global public good that deal with transboundary externalities, climate finance may target countries with high CO2 emissions to reduce long-term climate warming.

To deal with this endogeneity bias we focuses on a specific category of instrumental variables; the Shift-Share instruments. The design of shift-share instruments is to create a composite instrument using two factors: a shock and a shock-sharing indicator. The shock is assumed to be exogenous due to its quasi-random assignment while the shock-sharing variable is allowed to be endogenous. According to Borusyak et al. (2022), the exogeneity of the shock is a sufficient condition for the validity of the shift-share instrument. In panel analysis, the fundamental idea of the method is to generate an instrumental variable that varies across both time and country. This is achieved by combining a time-specific variable (referred to as “shock”) with a country-specific variable (referred to as “shock-sharing”). This method has already been employed by scholars to address endogeneity issues in the assessment of development assistance effectiveness (Nunn and Qian, 2014; Chauvet and Ehrhart, 2018; Ahmed et al., 2016; Dreher and Langlotz, 2020).¹²

4.3 Empirical framework

Based on the predictions of the literature discussed above, we elaborate our empirical model by integrating three main groups of factors that previous research has identified as determinant of environmental quality. Our baseline model is aligned with

11. The Resilience and Sustainability Trust is an innovative and complement instrument of the existing IMF’s lending toolkit introduce in April 2022 and focus on longer-term structural challenges including climate change and pandemic preparedness that entail significant macroeconomic risks and where policy solutions have a strong global public good nature. It is a loan-based instrument, with purpose to mobilize resources on a voluntary basis. In practice, the RST consists in channeling Special Drawing Rights (SDRs) contributed by countries with strong external positions to countries where the needs are the greatest, providing policy support and affordable longer-term financing to strengthen members’ resilience and sustainability and thereby contributing to prospective balance of payments stability (IFM, 2024).

12. Nunn and Qian (2014) used this approach to investigate the relationship between U.S. food aid and civil conflict in recipient countries. Ahmed et al. (2016) exploited plausibly exogenous variation in the legislative fragmentation of the U.S. House of Representatives to construct a powerful instrumental variable for U.S. bilateral aid disbursements. Similarly, Dreher and Langlotz (2020) employed legislative fragmentation in donor countries’ parliaments, interacted with the probability of recipient countries receiving aid, to build an instrumental variable for aid in order to examine the longstanding relationship between aid and economic growth in recipient countries. Chauvet and Ehrhart (2018) also use a composite instrument to address endogeneity concerns in the relationship between foreign aid and firm-level growth. They exploit exogenous variation in donor countries’ fiscal revenues, interacted with cultural or historical distance, to construct their composite instrument.

Lee et al. (2022) but augmented by others relevant variables identified as a key determinant of the environmental quality. We also specify a log-log model to read the estimated coefficient as an elasticity. The baseline model is then presented as follows :

$$\log(CFP_{i,t}) = \beta_i + \beta_1 \log(CF_{i,t}) + \gamma_x X_{i,t} + \nu_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Where $CFP_{i,t}$ and $CF_{i,t}$ respectively represent the carbon footprint per capita and the climate funds as a percentage of the GDP of country i at year t and $X_{i,t}$ a list of control variables presented above. β_i represents the country-specific effects, ν_t the time period fixed effects that capture the common shocks to all countries and $\epsilon_{i,t}$, the error term. β_1 ¹³ and γ_x respectively denote the coefficients associated to climate finance and the various control variables. Following the predictions of the economic literature, we expect β_1 to be negative, meaning that climate finance reduces the carbon footprint of the beneficiary countries.

Our first-stage equation is given by:

$$CF_{i,t} = \alpha IV_{i,t} + \sigma_x X_{i,t} + \eta_i + \phi_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

Where $IV_{i,t}$ is our composite instrumental variable, representing the interaction between a country-specific variable for recipients ($Prob_i$) and a donor-specific variable ($treat_j$). Since the identity of donor countries varies over time for each recipient, $treat_j$ effectively becomes a time-specific variable ($treat_t$) from the recipient's perspective. η_i , ϕ_t and $\epsilon_{i,t}$ respectively design the country fixed effect, the time period fixed effects and the error term. The coefficient α and σ_x respectively represent the effect of our instrumental variable and control variables on climate finance.

4.4 Instrumental variable setting

To construct our instrumental variable, we employ the cumulative number of environmental treaties ratified by donor countries from 1815 to 2016 as an exogenous shock variable. We interpret this indicator as the degree of the donor country's commitment to climate issues, thus indicating its willingness to provide more climate finance to developing countries. The cumulative number of environmental treaties ratified by donor countries is calculated as follows: $Treat_{j1} = \sum_{t=1815}^{2016} (Treat_{i,j} - Treat_i)$, where $Treat_{j1}$ represents the total number of environmental treaties ratified by each donor country during the period, $Treat_{i,j}$ denotes all treaties ratified from 1815 to 2016, and $Treat_i$ refers to the treaties that involve the recipient countries. We exclude treaties that involve recipient countries to comply with the exclusion restriction criterion, essential for valid instrument construction in our econometric analysis. To perform our instrumental variable and ensure compliance with the exclusion restriction hypothesis, we specifically count environmental treaties excluding those focused on pollution reduction objectives and we restrict our analysis to treaties signed between 1815 and 1996 in order to exclude the post-Kyoto period, which introduced the first quantified emission reduction targets. We compute this indicator using the following formula : $Treat_{j2} = \sum_{t=1815}^{1996} (Treat_{i,j} - Treat_i - Treat_p)$. Where $Treat_p$ refers to the treaties that target pollution as objectives.

We use the stock of treaties rather than the treaties ratified each year for three primary reasons. First, the database for environmental treaties only extends up to 2016, which significantly diverges from our period of analysis. Second, counting the treaties ratified annually could introduce bias, as countries may withdraw from treaties from one year to the next. For

13. We tested the non-linear specification by including the squared term of GDP per capita, in line with the Environmental Kuznets Curve framework (Grossman and Krueger, 1991; Dinda, 2004), but the coefficient associated with the quadratic term is statistically insignificant.

example the U.S. exiting and then re-entering in the Paris Agreement under different administrations, highlight the political influence on countries' commitments to international climate agreements. Third, many of these agreements were established before our study period. Restricting our analysis to treaties ratified within our study period could lead to censorship biases, which might undermine the reliability of our instrument. Research indicates that the ratification of environmental treaties by a country may signify its dedication to addressing climate issues, given the commitments embedded within these treaties. While factors such as, trade restrictions, penalties, legalization and institutional flexibility of treaties may affect a country's decision to ratify (Von Stein, 2008; Bellelli et al., 2023; Sauquet, 2014), Von Stein (2008) considers ratification as essential for improving the environmental practices and efforts of countries. Indeed, a country that ratifies a treaty undertakes two fundamental responsibilities: to develop national action plans aimed at achieving the treaty's goals and to establish a national inventory system to monitor these objectives over time. For example, for the Kyoto protocol, each country had an obligation to prepare national action plans for controlling emissions and create national emissions inventories (Von Stein, 2008). A country's ratification of treaties that impose strict conditions—encompassing not only domestic emission reductions but also the financial responsibilities as specified in the Paris Agreement—demonstrates its dedication to combat climate change. From this perspective, we use the total number of ratified environmental treaties by donor nations as a reflection of their willingness to address climate change, which in turn functions as a catalyst for its climate finance directed towards developing countries. The intuition behind is that countries making efforts at the national level to improve the quality of the environment will be more inclined to allocate funds to developing countries to fight against climate change given that climate stability is a global public good. We therefore expect the stock of treaties to be positively correlated with climate finance budgets at donors level.

Regarding the shock-sharing variable, we proxy a country's probability of receiving bilateral climate finance with the percentage of years the country received climate finance from a particular donor over the sample period, following Nunn and Qian (2014), Ahmed et al. (2016) and Dreher and Langlotz (2020). Specifically, the probability of receiving climate aid from a particular donor is :

$Prob_{i,j} = \frac{1}{21} \sum_{t=1}^{21} CF_{i,j}$, where i represents the recipient country, j the donor country and $CF_{i,j}$ indicating whether recipient i received climate finance from donor j in year t . We then compute, for each country i , an average probability of receiving funding from all donors, making the probability recipient-specific ($Prob_{i1}$).

Since the method used to compute the probability of receiving funds accounts for the frequency with which a country receives support from its donor partners—effectively capturing the strength of donor-recipient relationships—we complement our analysis with a theoretical probability to assess the robustness of our empirical results. This approach allows us to remove the degree of proximity between donors and recipient countries, making our probability measure more exogenous than the previous one.

The theoretical probability is calculated at the donor level by considering the number N of recipient countries funded by a given donor in a specific year. We assume that each recipient has an equal probability of $1/N$ of receiving funds from donor j .

An average probability over the entire period is then computed as follows:

$$Prob_{i2} = \frac{1}{21ND} \sum_{j=1}^n CF_j$$

where N is the number of recipient countries that received climate finance from donor j in year t , D is the number of donors providing funds to recipient i each year, n is the total number of donors, and CF_j is a binary indicator equal to 1 if recipient i received climate finance from donor j , and 0 otherwise.

After computing the theoretical probability ($\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^n CF_j$), we average this over all donors and years to obtain a recipient-specific probability ($Prob_{i,2} = \frac{1}{21ND} \sum_{j=1}^n CF_j$).

Following [Dreher and Langlotz \(2020\)](#), our instrument exploits the exogenous variation resulting from a differential effect of irregular donor-government ratification of environmental treaties on climate finance for recipient countries. In line with this assumption, we motivate the components of our interacted instruments in [table 2](#) and [figure 2](#). We expect that the extent to which increased donor climate aid budgets — induced by the ratification of environmental treaties — affect climate finance revenues at recipient level will depend on the likelihood of a country receiving aid. Indeed, the literature highlights that the probability of receiving foreign aid is significantly correlated with the amount of aid a country receives ([Ahmed et al., 2016](#); [Nunn and Qian, 2014](#); [Dreher and Langlotz, 2020](#)).

Table 2 – *Correlation Between Environmental Treaties and Donors’ Climate Finance*

	Total climate finance	Adaptation	Mitigation	Treat	Treat2
Total climate finance	1				
Adaptation	0.7284*	1			
Mitigation	0.9664*	0.5432*	1		
Treat1	0.1649*	0.2345*	0.1346*	1	
Treat2	0.0827*	0.1393*	0.0541	0.7015*	1

Note: This table reports the correlation coefficients between climate finance variables and two proxies for donor engagement in international environmental agreements: the number of environmental treaties ratified (Treat) and an alternative measure (Treat2). The objective is to examine the extent to which donors’ treaty participation is associated with their climate finance funds. ** indicates significance at the 1% level.

Figure 2 – *Probability to receive Finance and recipient climate finance*

Source: Author Calculation from OECD and EORA data.

The results presented in table 2 and figure 2 show that our hypotheses are verified. Ratification of environmental treaties (Treat) acts as a lever for climate finance at the donor level due to the positive correlation between this indicator and the different climate finance variables (see figure 16 for Prob2). The correlation seems stronger for adaptation funding than those of mitigation and total climate finance. The probability is also directly correlated to the funding received by developing countries. Certainly, the amount of climate finance a recipient country receives increases with the number of relationships it has with various donor countries; in other words, when its average probability is relatively high.

By combining the two variables $Treat_t$ and $Prob_i$, we obtain an instrumental variable that varies over time and across countries. It is important to remember that the stock of treaties ratified (Treat) is invariant over time at the donor level. However, given that donor countries vary across time for a given recipient country, Treat becomes variable over time at the recipient level, making thus our instrumental variable varying over time. The instrumental variable for our baseline model presents as follows :

$$IV_{i,t} = Prob_i \times Treat_t \quad (3)$$

Given that the two components of our instrumental variable are positively correlate to climate finance we expect the instrumental variable to be positively related to the funding received by the recipients. The figure below supports this hypothesis (see figure 17 and 18 in the appendix for IV2 and IV3), showing a positive correlation between the instrument and the various climate finance variables although the significance and the strength of this relationship is to be confirmed in the econometric estimates by the first-stage equation.

Figure 3 – Instrumental Variable(IV) and recipient climate finance

Source: Author Calculation from OECD and IEA data.

5 Empirical Results and Discussion

5.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics presented in table 12 show that the average per capita carbon footprint is 3.62, with a range from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 18.11 gigatons of CO₂ equivalent. The carbon footprint data from the World Inequality Database (WID) displays statistics that are consistent with the main source of carbon footprint from EORA, thus reinforcing the reliability of the data utilized for our analysis. The carbon intensity of GDP shows an average of 1596.6, with values ranging from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 18809.7. Countries such as Palestine and Sudan have zero values for carbon footprint and carbon intensity of GDP, likely due to the unavailability of data for these countries in the source used for some years. Regarding the ecological footprint, the average value is 1.96 hectares per capita, with a minimum of 0.27 and a maximum of 8.68. Our various climate finance variables are highly dispersed, exhibiting high standard deviations. This justifies our choice of the log-log model to mitigate the effect of outliers on our estimations. The components of the instrumental variables align with our expectations, with the various probabilities ranging from 0.02 to 0.6. For additional details on other variables, see Table 12 in the appendix.

To ensure the stationarity of our variables of interest, climate finance and carbon footprint, we conducted unit root tests following Maddala and Wu (1999). We chose this test due to its robustness in handling missing data. The results of

these tests, presented in Table 15, indicate that the variables are stationary. This reinforces our confidence that the effect isolated in the empirical section is indeed the effect of climate finance. Given that we use multiple variables from the same sector such as access to electricity, energy intensity, renewable energy, and fossil fuels in our empirical analysis, we also test the correlation between these variables to avoid redundancy. The findings illustrated in Tables 13 and 14 reveal favorable correlation coefficients, suggesting that we can use these variable in the same equation. Notably, the highest coefficient observed, reaching 0.99, reflects the correlation between the probability to receive climate finance and the instrumental variables.

5.2 Baseline estimations

Table 3 reports the results of IV-2SLS estimations of the baseline econometric model (Equation 1) on the sample of 75 developing countries.

First-stage statistics support the quality of our instrumental variable (IV) in baseline estimations since the Kleibergen-Paap F-statistic exceeds the critical value at all conventional significance levels for all baseline estimates except column 11. The first stage estimates reported in Panel B show that our IV also have the expected sign. This provides evidence on the strength of the instrument used in this analysis. The strength of our instrumental variable reassures us of the validity of our results, as supported by the literature on plausibly exogenous instruments. It is well known that the sensitivity of the 2SLS estimator to violations of the exclusion restriction depends on the strength of the instruments. For example, relatively minor deviations from the exclusion restriction can greatly decrease precision when instruments are weak, while large deviations may have only a small influence on precision when the instruments are strong (Conley et al., 2012).

The second-stage estimates show results that are consistent with those of previous studies. We start by estimating our model without including control variables to measure the effect of climate finance without variables (column (1)). We chose to include the variables one by one until we find our main model. This approach helps ensure that we capture the individual contributions of each variable to the regression and maintaining statistical robustness of our key parameter .

Column 1 demonstrates that climate finance significantly reduces the carbon footprint of recipient countries at a 1% significance level. Specifically, a 1% increase in climate finance results in a 0.09% reduction in their carbon footprint. This effect remain significant when we control for socio-economic variables such as GDP per capita, population growth, and public and private investment, respectively, in columns 2, 3, 4, and 5. GDP per capita and private investment significantly increase CO2 emissions at the 1 and 5% threshold, while population growth and public investment are only significant at 10% threshold effect for some columns. We observe a reduction in the number of observations in columns 4 and 5 due to the exclusion of missing values from the sample. The impact of economic activity and private investment aligns with the theoretical predictions of the green growth model of Brock and Taylor (2010), which demonstrate that per capita income and investment are among the primary determinants of emissions. In column 6, we introduce trade openness to account for the influence of the country’s trade activities on its carbon footprint, given that the carbon footprint includes emissions related to trade. We observe a nonsignificant effect of trade activity on the carbon footprint across all estimates of the basic model. To take into account the effect of population concentration on CO2 emissions we introduce the rate of urbanization which is supposed to have a positive effect on carbon emission due to the multiplication of informal activities and the challenges related to waste management. Column 7 reveals a counter intuitive effect, showing that the urbanization rate significantly reduces emissions at the 1% and 10% threshold across all estimates. Although counter intuitive, this effect is consistent with

[Aquilas and Atemnkeng \(2022\)](#) and could be explained by the fact that urbanization often comes with agglomeration effects, leading to process innovations in production and improved waste management ([Lee et al., 2022](#); [Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022](#)).

Incorporating industrial added value in columns 8 reveals that this indicator positively impact the environmental quality of recipient countries by significantly increasing the carbon footprint. These results are consistent with those from [Lee et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Zoungrana et al. \(2024\)](#), which also demonstrate a positive effect of industrialization on emissions. We can observe again a reduction in the number of observations in columns 7 and 8, which is associated with missing values. Additionally, we control for access to electricity which are known in economic studies to significantly influence CO2 emissions ([Carfora et al., 2017](#)). Energy is indeed one of the most polluting sectors, accounting for the highest share of emissions globally. This is particularly concerning in developing countries, where access to clean energy is limited. Columns 9 shows that in our analysis, the impact of access to electricity on CO2 emissions is not statistically significant. To account for other source of finance, we include foreign direct investment (FDI) in column 10. The effect of foreign direct investment (FDI) on carbon emissions is well-documented in economic literature ([Wang and Zhang, 2022](#); [Zheng et al., 2024](#)). FDI tends to reduce carbon emissions by enhancing the efficiency of production systems through advanced technologies transfer ([Wang and Zhang, 2022](#)). However, result shows that FDI positively impact CO2 emission, suggesting that under the period FDI was mainly directed toward emitting sectors. Column 10 is our baseline model. It shows that climate finance improves the environmental quality of recipient countries by reducing their carbon footprint. A 1% increase in climate finance reduces the carbon footprint by 0.051%. This result corroborates findings from previous studies that have evaluated the effect of climate finance ([Carfora et al., 2017](#); [Boly, 2018](#); [Carfora and Scandurra, 2019](#); [Lee et al., 2022](#); [Zhang et al., 2021](#)). Although the size of our coefficient of interest is relatively small—partly because we use different units from previous studies to measure CO2 emissions and climate finance, and also due to the time lag from commitment finance to be disbursed—the direction of the relationship remains consistent. Column 11 addresses this limitation by displaying the regression results of our baseline model using disbursed climate finance data, which show a more strong effect than those obtained with commitment data. This difference can be attributed to the time lag associated with the disbursement of climate funds. According to the literature, it typically takes an average of four years for aid to manifest its effects on the outcomes of recipient countries ([Nunn and Qian, 2014](#); [Ahmed et al., 2016](#); [Dreher and Langlotz, 2020](#); [Lee et al., 2022](#)).

Table 3 – Baseline estimates

Variable : Carbon Footprint	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
Panel A: Second stage											
Climate Finance (log)	-0.091***	-0.072***	-0.071***	-0.075***	-0.055***	-0.057***	-0.048***	-0.047**	-0.048**	-0.051**	
	(0.020)	(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.021)	(0.018)	(0.019)	(0.017)	(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.021)	
Disbursed finance (log)											-0.087*
											(0.047)
GDP Per capita (log)		0.403***	0.403***	0.406***	0.495***	0.494***	0.529***	0.520***	0.519***	0.523***	0.553***
		(0.064)	(0.063)	(0.067)	(0.060)	(0.060)	(0.063)	(0.070)	(0.071)	(0.076)	(0.075)
Demographic Growth			0.014	0.013	0.017*	0.016*	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.013	0.027***
			(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)
Private Investment (log)				0.066**	0.064**	0.062**	0.067***	0.076***	0.076***	0.056*	-0.035
				(0.028)	(0.027)	(0.027)	(0.026)	(0.027)	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.039)
Public Investment (log)					-0.020	-0.021	-0.025*	-0.029*	-0.029*	-0.024	-0.021
					(0.015)	(0.014)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.019)
Trade openness (log)						0.022	0.024	0.030	0.031	0.029	0.082
						(0.036)	(0.035)	(0.039)	(0.039)	(0.040)	(0.065)
Urbanization Rate (log)							-0.444***	-0.531***	-0.534***	-0.549***	-0.386*
							(0.160)	(0.177)	(0.177)	(0.182)	(0.209)
Industry Value Added								0.771*	0.769*	0.759*	0.754
								(0.408)	(0.409)	(0.431)	(0.536)
Access to Electricity									0.081	0.074	0.224
									(0.123)	(0.129)	(0.194)
FDI										0.237*	0.285*
										(0.128)	(0.153)
Observations	1296	1296.	1296	1248	1201	1201	1201	1152	1152	1141	1053
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes									
R ²	0.954	0.081	0.094	0.090	0.228	0.221	0.272	0.263	0.262	0.248	0.960
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	37.052	32.202	31.664	26.579	27.354	24.970	27.723	21.903	21.100	18.948	5.086
Panel B: First Stage											
IV(TreatXProb)	0.036***	0.033***	0.032***	0.030***	0.031***	0.030***	0.032***	0.029***	0.029***	0.027***	0.028***
	(0.009)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.007)

Note : This table presents the results of our baseline model. We introduce variables one by one to account for the marginal effect of each variable on our coefficient of interest. Column 1 shows the bivariate effect of climate finance on the carbon footprint. Columns 2 to 10 measure the additional effect of each variable on the regression by including country-Year fixed effects to smooth out the effect of common shocks that affect all the countries in the sample and help to better understand the marginal influence of each variable on the number of observations. Column 11 presents the disbursed finance. Robust Standard errors in parentheses, * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

5.3 Robustness checks

5.3.1 Additional controls

In order to test the robustness of our results, we consider additional relevant determinants of environmental quality beyond our main model. We introduce variables such as the country's endowment with natural carbon sinks measured by forest area, Carbon Intensity of energy, the proportion of women in parliament, inequality measured by the Gini index, revenues from natural resources, and governance indicator measured by the corruption index.

The inclusion of forest area as a variable is justified by the consideration that countries endowed with substantial forest resources potentially possess a higher capacity to absorb emissions compared to those with limited forest areas. Forests can also be seen as a source of rent for developing countries, given their severe budget constraints, often leading to large-

scale exploitation and exposing them to a trade-off between environmental protection and macroeconomic stability (Combes et al., 2015). Political economy models also theoretically suggest that higher income inequality contributes to increased environmental degradation (Borghesi et al., 2006; Ravallion et al., 2000; Berthe and Elie, 2015). Ravallion et al. (2000) assert that the effect of income inequality on environmental degradation depends on the marginal propensity to emit (MPE). They argue that if the poor exhibit a higher MPE than the rich, decreasing income inequality could lead to an increase in pollution emissions. Recent studies have also shown that corruption governance has a moderating effect on the relationship between income inequality and carbon emissions (Wang et al., 2024b). Regarding corruption and natural resource rents, previous studies offer mixed conclusions about the impact of resource-related rents and governance (Li et al., 2024; Khan and Hassan, 2024). For example, the extraction and combustion of fossil fuels, such as oil, gas and coal, releases large amounts of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Control of corruption effectively addresses the problem of CO2 emissions (Khan and Hassan, 2024). Given this, and taking into account that our study period encompasses the commodity supercycle (2001-2007), we include the resource rents as an additional control variable to capture the influence of the commodity supercycle on our results. Table 4 indicates that our results are consistent upon including these variables and reveals that only the country's Carbon Intensity of energy significantly increase CO2 emission at 1 and 5% its carbon footprint .

Table 4 – *Robustness Test: Additional controls*

Variable : Carbon Footprint	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Panel A : Second stage								
Climate Finance (log)	-0.051** (0.021)	-0.051** (0.021)	-0.058*** (0.020)	-0.062*** (0.022)	-0.056*** (0.020)	-0.057*** (0.021)	-0.058*** (0.021)	-0.058** (0.023)
Forest Area		-0.001 (0.017)	-0.003 (0.018)	-0.005 (0.019)	-0.009 (0.018)	-0.009 (0.018)	-0.009 (0.018)	-0.092 (0.057)
Carbon Intensity of energy			0.162*** (0.061)	0.150** (0.068)	0.170*** (0.065)	0.170*** (0.065)	0.209*** (0.074)	0.270*** (0.084)
Woman share in Parliament				-0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)
Gini index					0.228 (0.249)	0.231 (0.249)	0.309 (0.271)	-0.205 (0.287)
Natural Ressource Rent						0.002 (0.002)	0.002 (0.002)	0.003 (0.002)
Renewable Energy Consumption							0.079 (0.083)	0.101 (0.086)
Corruption index								0.012 (0.013)
Observations	1141	1141	1141	1105	1097	1097	1097	894
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.248	0.248	0.222	0.208	0.237	0.236	0.235	0.263
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	18.948	18.487	21.048	19.153	20.224	20.222	19.842	19.416
Panel B:First Stage								
IV (Treat × Prob)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.029*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.008)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.029*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.008)	0.029*** (0.008)

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

5.3.2 Alternative variables of environmental quality and IV

For the sensitivity analysis, we have selected alternative measures of environmental quality as dependent variables to check the robustness of our initial findings. First, we use the carbon footprint data from the World Inequality Database, which also employs the consumption-based approach to quantify the carbon footprint across nations. We alter the data source to account for the potential impact of measurement errors on our parameters estimation (Stefanski, 1985; Armstrong, 1985). Furthermore, we assess environmental performance using the carbon intensity of GDP. This indicator is especially relevant as a primary aim of climate finance is to foster sustainable development. It is hypothesized that increased climate finance will lead to a reduction in carbon intensity, reflecting improvements in economic efficiency and a shift towards less carbon-intensive industries. In addition, the ecological footprint is utilized as it comprehensively measures human pressure on resources and ecosystems by comparing resource demand with the planet’s biocapacity. This broader measure allows us to capture not only carbon emissions but also other aspects of ecological demand such as land use and water consumption. Finally, we use the Environmental Performance Index (EPI), a synthetic indicator of environmental sustainability, to test the robustness of our results.

Table 5 – *Alternative variables of environmental quality and IV*

Variable :	Baseline	CFP_WID	CI_GDP	Ecological Footprint	EPI	CFP	CFP
Panel A: Second stage							
Climate Finance (log)	-0.051** (0.021)	-0.044* (0.025)	-0.070** (0.031)	-0.015** (0.007)	0.037*** (0.008)	-0.056* (0.030)	-0.142*** (0.046)
Observations	1141	1144	1141	1141	703	1141	1141
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.248	0.336	0.712	0.308	0.529	0.225	0.389
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	18.948	18.760	18.948	80.960	90.259	9.974	75.636
Panel B: First Stage							
IV(Treat1XProb1)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.027*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.009)		
IV2(Treat1XProb2)						0.029** (0.012)	
IV3(Treat2XProb1)							0.013* (0.007)

Note: This table reports the effects of climate finance on alternative outcome variables. For the EPI, we control for the full set of covariates given its multidimensional nature. CFP: Carbon Footprint; CFP_WID: Carbon Footprint from the World Inequality Database; CI_GDP: Carbon Intensity of GDP. Standard errors in parentheses * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

The results, detailed Table 5, indicate that climate finance significantly decreases both carbon intensity of GDP, and ecological footprint, with statistical significance at the 5% levels. These findings indicate that climate finance can act as a catalyst for green growth, primarily by facilitating the transition toward low-carbon production systems (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019). The effect on ecological footprint is consistent with previous studies that find also a negative impact of climate finance on ecological footprint (Zougrana et al., 2024). We can also note that climate finance positively impact countries environmental performance index. The consistency in the sign and significance of these results with our expectations

reinforces the hypothesis that climate finance effectively contributes to environmental sustainability. Despite the closeness in coefficients for carbon footprint and carbon intensity across different model specifications, the ecological footprint presents a notable variance. Climate finance also enhances the environmental performance of recipient countries, albeit with a lower coefficient compared to that associated with the carbon footprint. This disparity for synthetic measurements of environmental quality suggest that while climate finance strongly influences carbon emissions, its impact on broader ecological changes—such as land and water use—is potentially less pronounced due to the fact that synthetic measurements of environmental quality combine several aspects of climate change.

In the last two columns , we introduce alternative instrumental variables: the interaction between the theoretical probability of receiving climate finance and the stock of environmental treaties ratified by donor countries(Treat1 and Treat2). The inclusion of this variable is intended to address potential endogeneity concerns by leveraging exogenous variations provided by international environmental commitments. The coefficient of this variable underscores the robustness of our primary findings. This further validation of the parameter of interest supports the effectiveness of climate finance to improve the recipient countries environmental quality.

5.3.3 Dynamic Effects of Climate Finance-local Projection Method

The static model presented in the baseline analysis helps us understand how climate finance affects emissions in the short term. However, it doesn't tell us whether this effect plays out over time or is more persistent. In fact, it's likely that emissions respond to climate finance with some delay, a pattern that aligns with findings from the broader foreign aid literature (Nunn and Qian, 2014; Ahmed et al., 2016; Dreher and Langlotz, 2020). This means we need to look beyond just the immediate impact and consider how effects unfold in later years.

Some studies have tried to account for this by including lagged climate finance variables or smoothing data over several years (Lee et al., 2022). Others have used GMM (Generalized Method of Moments) techniques to estimate the dynamic relationship (Boly, 2018; Lee et al., 2022; Zoungrana et al., 2024). But these approaches have clear limitations. They tend to be sensitive to errors in model design and don't offer a clear picture of how the effects of climate finance evolve over time. Moreover, GMM methods can fall when the impact of climate finance is persistent. In such situations, the internal instruments used in GMM become weak, which can lead to biased results (Kruiniger, 2009) . Also, GMM only account for the persistence of outcomes but not for the dynamic effects of climate finance itself (Kruiniger, 2009) and does not allow us to clearly show how the effect changes from year to year, making it hard to understand the real dynamic of climate finance.

For these reasons, we perform the previous analysis on dynamics effect, using the local projection method (LPM) proposed by Jordà (2005), which we combine with our instrumental variable approach. The main advantage of this method is its flexibility in capturing the time-varying response of variables to shocks or policy interventions, without requiring strong assumptions about the underlying data generation process (Jordà, 2005; Plagborg-Møller and Wolf, 2021; Kpodar and Imam, 2024). This method allows for the estimation of impulse response functions (IRFs) over multiple horizons, providing insights into both the immediate and long-term effects of climate finance. LPM is widely used to estimate the dynamic effects of the interaction between policy interventions and outcomes (Jalles, 2020, 2023; Huang and Punzi, 2024; Kpodar and Imam, 2024).

Using a local projection method, we find in Figure 4 and Table 11 that climate finance has a negative and statistically significant impact on CO2 emissions. The impulse response function (IRF) shows a clear and gradual negative effect of

climate finance on CO2 emissions. Right after climate finance shock (period 0), emissions start to decrease slightly, and the reduction becomes more strong over time, reaching a peak around period 4. From that point, the effect gradually fades but remains negative up to period 8, suggesting a nonlinear effect of climate finance on CO2 emission over time. The 95% confidence intervals suggest that this effect is statistically significant from period 1 to period 8 (with a small exception at period 2), the upper bounds of the confidence intervals remain below or very close to zero. This indicates that the observed effects are unlikely to be driven by random noise and supports the robustness of the estimated relationship. Moreover, this effect is close to the findings of development aid literature that show that aid take around 4 years to be effective on developing countries economics outcomes (Nunn and Qian, 2014; Ahmed et al., 2016; Dreher and Langlotz, 2020). Just after the ninth year (period 8), the effect of climate finance on emissions becomes statistically insignificant, with residual negative effects observed in the eleventh (period 10) and eighteenth (period 17) years following the shock (see figure 5). This suggests that increased climate finance contributes to reducing emissions, potentially through slower transmission mechanisms particularly in sectors like forest and energy sector where investments take time to translate into emission reductions. Economically, these finding support the view that climate finance is an effective tool for reducing emissions, particularly in the medium term, but also highlight the importance of sustained and well-targeted investments and the cooperation of local communities to ensure long-lasting impact (Blake, 1999; Feng and Reisner, 2011).

Figure 4 – *Impulse Response Function*

5.4 Heterogeneity Analysis

In this section, we explore the heterogeneity of our findings by examining various dimensions: the type of finance (adaptation, mitigation, multilateral), the financial instruments used to allocate climate funds (debt vs grant instrument), the impact of debt burden and innovation capacity measured by residents patents application. Table 6 reveals that mitigation finance significantly influences carbon footprint reduction. In contrast, neither adaptation funds nor multilateral financing show significant effects. The non significant effect of adaptation-related finance is not surprising as these funds are often directed

toward projects whose primary objective is not necessarily the reduction of CO2 emissions in the medium term.

Our results appear counterintuitive for multilateral finance given the general literature on aid effectiveness, which tends to favor multilateral aid over bilateral aid. Indeed, multilateral aid is often viewed as more effective due to pro-development conditionality (Burnside and Dollar, 2000), its greater legitimacy in the eyes of recipient countries (Bird et al., 2000), lower fragmentation (Addison et al., 2015), and the expertise and specialization of multilateral agencies (Askarov and Doucouliagos, 2013).

Focusing on the environmental aid effectiveness these findings diverges from previous research, such as the studies by Boly (2018) and Lee et al. (2022), which report significant reductions in CO2 emissions due to multilateral financing in recipient countries. Furthermore, contrary to the findings by Lee et al. (2022), which observed a weak impact of adaptation funds, our analysis indicates that these funds do not significantly affect the carbon footprint. Several economic explanations can account for these findings. The lack of a significant effect from multilateral climate finance may be due to the fact that bilateral institutions tend to support more targeted projects that are better adapted to specific national contexts. This alignment with local needs can facilitate more effective implementation and yield more concrete environmental outcomes. In contrast, multilateral institutions are often associated with heavier bureaucratic procedures and allocation criteria that are less responsive to local priorities, which may undermine their effectiveness (Atteridge et al., 2009). Furthermore, the nature of the financial instruments used in allocating climate funds may also play a crucial role. When aid is delivered in the form of debt, it can encourage fungibility behavior, whereby recipient countries reallocate part of the climate funds to meet debt servicing obligations. Conversely, grants are less likely to induce such behavior. Our data support this hypothesis: multilateral climate finance is predominantly provided as loans—both in terms of number of project and volume of finance—whereas bilateral finance relies mainly on grants (see figure 14 and 15 in appendix). We also explore new forms of heterogeneity that have not yet been addressed in the existing literature

First, we introduce a novel aspect by examining the heterogeneity associated with the financial instrument used in climate financing. We hypothesize that financing through debt instruments might inadvertently lead to increased carbon emissions while grant funding reduces emissions. This could occur if the obligation to repay the debt with interest prompts recipient countries to allocate funds towards activities that are less efficient in terms of carbon reduction, driven by the need to ensure economic returns that can cover their debt service. Furthermore, existing literature demonstrates that, in the long term, public debt and environmental debt are complementary, as interest payments tend to crowd out public expenditures dedicated to environmental protection (Boly et al., 2022). The results shown in columns 5 and 6 of table 6 confirm our hypothesis, revealing that only grant funding significantly reduces the carbon footprint. This finding suggests that the type of financial instrument plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of climate finance, with grants leading to more sustainable environment compared to debt financing. Column 7 displays the result of grant instrument on the number of observation of debt finance in order to make them comparable.

Table 6 – *Heterogeneous effect : Type of finance and financial instrument*

Variable : Carbon Footprint	(Baseline)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Climate Finance (log)	-0.051** (0.021)						
Mitigation Finance (log)		-0.041** (0.016)					
Adaptation Finance (log)			-0.018 (0.033)				
Multilateral Finance(log)				-0.014 (0.044)			
Debt Instrument					-0.157 (0.191)		
Grant Instrument						-0.053** (0.021)	-0.050* (0.027)
Observations	1141	1140	602	581	427	1140	418
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.248	0.264	0.114	0.977	0.909	0.256	0.610
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	18.948	24.686	6.697	2.032	0.658	24.029	14.035

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Second, we also explore the heterogeneity of results according to the innovation capacity measured by country patents application. The sample is segmented based on the median number of patent application. Our results indicate a significant divergence in how climate finance contributes to reducing the carbon footprint of these groups. For countries with high innovation capacity, the impact of climate finance on reducing carbon emissions is notably more pronounced (table 7). This suggests that pre-existing innovation policies and investment amplify the effectiveness of climate finance, potentially due to better infrastructure and regulatory frameworks that facilitate the implementation of financed projects.

Third, we investigate how the outcomes vary depending on the burden of debt, measured by the ratio of debt interest payments to GDP. The intuition behind this analysis is that countries with unhealthy public finances, characterized by high interest rates, are less effective in managing climate funds due to the pressure of debt servicing on public finances. This could not only result in a compositional effect in budget planning, reducing the share of environmental spending in public finances, but also lead to climate funds being directed towards less sustainable projects to generate sufficient returns for debt repayment. Our findings reveal that countries with lower debt burdens use climate finance more effectively; the impact is significant in these nations but not in countries with a higher debt load. This result suggests that healthy public finances is a prerequisite for the effective use of climate funds. A debt relief program for developing countries could also yield international environmental benefits by reducing CO₂ emissions and reducing environmental debt because an increase in general debt is linked to a rise in environmental debt in long run (Boly et al., 2022).

By using total official development assistance (ODA) to investigate the specific effect of climate finance, we show that total aid substantially reduces CO₂ emissions, although its effect is relatively minor compared to aid specifically targeted climate objectives. This result allows us to infer that the effect estimated in the baseline is an effect attributable to climate funds given that total aid incurs climate funds and that the literature provides evidence on the inefficiency of overall aid to reduce CO₂ emissions (Boly, 2018; Wang et al., 2024a).

To account for financial support received from other emerging donors, we include Chinese aid directed toward environmental objectives, given China’s growing role in international finance and, more specifically, in global aid since the early 2000s (Horn et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024a). For comparison, between 2000 and 2018, China provided approximately \$354.4 billion in aid to 140 countries and regions worldwide, whereas U.S. foreign aid over the same period amounted to \$394.6 billion. Beyond this increasing volume, Chinese authorities have explicitly committed to greening their development assistance, thereby assuming greater international responsibility in promoting the concept of green development (China, 2021).¹⁴

For these reasons, we estimate the impact of Chinese environmental finance on greenhouse gas emissions in recipient countries. The results in the last column of Table 7 show that Chinese aid significantly reduces the carbon footprint of recipient countries at the 10% significance level. Although the effect is statistically significant, the coefficient is smaller than that of DAC members’ climate finance. This may be attributed to the weakness of chinese finance and the fact that, during the sample period, Chinese aid was less explicitly targeted toward climate-related objectives (see Tables 14 and 15). This finding highlights a specific effect of climate-oriented finance, as previous studies have shown that overall Chinese aid does not significantly reduce recipient countries’ carbon emissions (Wang et al., 2024a).

These results underscore the importance of tailored approaches to climate financing. They suggest that international donors and financial institutions should consider the innovation capacities and policy environments of recipient countries when allocating climate funds. Enhancing innovation ecosystems and strengthening macroeconomic policy enforcement in countries with low capacity could increase the effectiveness of climate finance, thereby better aligning financial flows with global emission reduction goals. The IMF’s Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST) serves as an example of a financial instrument that integrates environmental and macroeconomic criteria into its financing conditions (IFM, 2024).

Table 7 – *Heterogeneous effect : Inovation Capacity and debt Burden*

Variable : Carbon Footprint	Innovation Capacity		Debt Burden		ODA	Chinese Finance
	(Low)	(High)	(Low)	(High)		
Climate Finance (log)	-0.014 (0.016)	-0.107*** (0.041)	-0.079** (0.039)	-0.048* (0.028)		
ODA(% of GDP)					-0.048** (0.022)	
Chinese Climate Finance						-0.014* (0.008)
Observations	545	672	393	741	1141	1260
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	9.064	10.973	8.834	7.300	7.642	6.751

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

14. In a report titled China’s International Development Cooperation in the New Era, China clearly outlines its ambition to align its development assistance with sustainable objectives, thereby contributing to the achievement of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

5.5 Does education matter for the climate finance effect ?

Research has highlighted in recent years the crucial role of education in the fight against climate change, prompting policymakers to implement climate education initiatives (Feng and Reisner, 2011; Kaiser et al., 2023). The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) assigns responsibility to the Convention’s parties to undertake public education and awareness campaigns on climate change and to ensure public participation in programs and access to information on the issue. Indeed, education could contribute to fight against climate change in several ways. Firstly, education raises awareness among people about environmental challenges such as climate change, deforestation, and pollution. With a better understanding of these issues, individuals are more likely to support and participate in initiatives aimed at addressing them (Feng and Reisner, 2011; UNDP, 2023). Secondly, education provides people with the knowledge and skills needed to adopt sustainable practices. For example, educated farmers may be more inclined to use environmentally friendly agricultural techniques that reduce soil erosion and water pollution. Thirdly, educated individuals are more likely to engage in policy advocacy and participate in decision-making processes related to environmental issues. Regarding climate finance, they can push for policies that promote sustainable development and ensure that climate finance is used effectively and transparently. Fourthly, education fosters innovation and the adoption of new technologies that can contribute to environmental sustainability. Educated entrepreneurs may develop clean energy solutions or implement efficient waste management systems, which can be supported by climate finance (Feng and Reisner, 2011). Finally, education enables people to better understand the long-term consequences of environmental degradation and the importance of resilience-building measures. Educated communities may invest in infrastructure projects that mitigate the impacts of climate change, such as flood defenses or drought-resistant agriculture.

To test these theoretical hypotheses, we analyze the heterogeneity of the climate finance effect based on the level of human capital in recipient countries. Since we use project-level data, the level of education appears important in explaining the effects of climate finance. As mentioned earlier, better-educated populations are able to take ownership of climate finance projects and advocate for project implementation to increase their effectiveness in long-term emissions reduction. To do this, we consider the net enrollment rates in primary, secondary, and tertiary education and we consider the average value of these different variables as a threshold for defining sub samples. The results from table 8 show that in countries with high levels of primary, secondary, and tertiary education, the effect of climate finance is significant, while it is non-significant in countries with low levels of education. Furthermore, we observe that within countries with high levels of education, the effect of climate finance is more significant for higher levels of education, with a more pronounced effect for tertiary education. This is because countries with high levels of tertiary education are able to conduct research related to climate change and find endogenous solutions to its adverse effects. A high rate of tertiary education also provides countries with innovation capacity and the opportunity to conduct climate change awareness and education campaigns for a wider audience, with intellectuals serving as trainers for local populations.

Table 8 – *Heterogeneous effect : Education matter for the climate finance effect*

Variable : Carbone Footprint						
	Primary school		Secondary school		Tertiary school	
	(Low)	(High)	(Low)	(High)	(Low)	(High)
Climate Finance (log)	0.063 (0.047)	-0.049** (0.023)	-0.174 (1.056)	-0.060*** (0.022)	0.014 (0.020)	-0.079*** (0.027)
Observations	229	908	238	902	512	620
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.000	0.290	0.000	0.240	0.490	0.190
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	3.870	16.172	0.024	21.141	5.343	18.898

Standard errors in parentheses.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

International initiatives such as the United Nations One UN Climate Change Learning Partnership (UN CC:Learn)¹⁵ promote climate change education for the general public as a solution to accelerate the fight against climate change. These results also suggest that all research collaborations aimed at enhancing the capacity of local actors constitute a source of strengthening the effectiveness of climate funds, highlighting the relevance of new capacity-building programs for developing countries such as Coalition for Capacity on Climate Action (C3A)¹⁶ and the United Nations One UN Climate Change Learning Partnership.

5.6 Transmission channel

In this section, we explore the economic mechanisms that may explain how climate finance impacts the environmental quality of recipient countries. According to our analysis, the potential pathways through which climate funds affect the environment are energy transition, reforestation and energy efficiency of GDP. To test this hypothesis, we employ the two-step method proposed by [Chauvet and Ehrhart \(2018\)](#). According to this approach, climate finance should promote the energy transition, increase forest area, and promote energy efficiency of production, which in turn ensure the environmental quality of the recipient countries. Initially, we conduct simple OLS regressions to examine the relationships between environmental quality and those variables. The energy transition is assessed through three indicators: first, the share of renewable energies in the total energy mix generation, considered as a measure of energy transition, secondly renewable energy consumption and the share of fossil fuel consumption in total energy consumption are used to account for energy pressures from the demand side. Subsequently, we use our instrumental variable of the baseline regression to address potential reverse causality between energy transition, forest area, energy efficiency of GDP and climate finance. The idea is that countries with substantial forest resources and high potential for renewable energy production are likely to attract more climate funds. To account for the lagged effect of climate finance on the energy transition and reforestation, as well as the impact of reforestation on environmental quality, we lag these variables by two periods. Our results indicate a positive and significant correlation between environmental quality and both renewable energy production, consumption and forest area, while a negative and

15. The One UN Climate Change Learning Partnership (UN CC:Learn) is a joint initiative of more than 30 multilateral organizations helping countries to achieve climate change action both through general climate literacy and applied skills development. UN CC:Learn provides strategic advice and quality learning resources to help people, governments and businesses to understand, adapt, and build resilience to climate change.

16. C3A is a knowledge-exchange and capacity-building program for Ministries of Finance that provides peer-to-peer exchanges, trainings on critical policy issues and collaboration on analytical tools.

significant correlation is observed with fossil fuel consumption. These findings suggest that transitioning to renewable energies, a primary target of climate funds, is a lever for improving environmental quality, unlike fossil fuels, which deteriorate it.

Table 9 – *Transmission channel*

Variables :	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
Climate Finance (log)	6.154*** (1.879)		0.840*** (0.103)		-10.080*** (1.916)		0.403*** (0.087)		0.0524** (0.022)	
Renewable energy Generation(1)		-0.005*** (0.001)								
Renewable energy Consumption(3)				-0.316*** (0.018)						
Fossil energy consumption (5)						0.004*** (0.001)				
Forest Area (7)								-0.046** (0.021)		
Energy Efficiency of GDP(9)										-0.427*** (0.052)
Observations	1040	1092	1040	1092	1040	1141	1040	1090	948	948
R ²	0.005	0.032		0.224		0.019		0.005	0.2075	0.5501
First-stage F-stat	10.722		66.308		27.675		21.652		21.90	

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Table 9 display the impact of climate finance on transmission indicators and the effect of these variables on the outcome, carbon footprint. The results show that climate finance significantly increases renewable energy production (column 1) and consumption (column 3) and significantly reduce fossil energy consumption (column 5). These results align with previous studies focused on the impact of climate funds on renewable energies (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019; Aquilas and Atemnkeng, 2022). These findings allow us to infer that energy transition is one of the channels through which climate finance improves environmental quality. As for forest area, climate finance significantly improve forest area (column 7) as a percentage of land area and forest area increases environmental quality by reducing carbon emission, suggesting that the increase of forest area (reforestation) is also a pathway through which climate finance enhances environmental quality.

Our findings further indicate that climate finance reduces carbon emissions by promoting a structural shift in the production systems of developing countries toward more sustainable trajectories. Specifically, it enhances the energy efficiency of GDP (column 9), implying a decoupling of economic growth from energy use and associated emissions. This result is relative to our previous finding on innovation capacity and particularly relevant in the context of the Paris Agreement, which seeks to promote ambitious climate action while simultaneously enhancing living standards and fostering sustainable development. In this sense, finance climate is seen as a source of green growth (Carfora and Scandurra, 2019), contributing to the simultaneous achievement of goals 8 and 13 of the 2030 Agenda. Columns 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively show the effect of renewable energy Generation, renewable energy Consumption, fossil energy consumption, forest area and energy efficiency of GDP on carbon footprint.

The synthesis of these results highlights that the impact of climate funds on environmental quality is mediated through energy transition, reforestation and energy efficiency improvement. This suggests that countries well-endowed with forest resources and with a high potential for renewable energy production and energy efficiency are those most likely to benefit

from climate funds for best environmental quality.

6 Conclusion and policy implication

Fight against climate change has become a global priority and is now a central part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This program recognizes the significant threats posed by climate change and emphasizes the urgent need for collective action by countries worldwide. To limit global warming to 2°C, CO₂ emissions must decrease rapidly and peak by 2030 (Lee et al., 2023). This goal is supported by various climate agreements, which collectively agree that climate finance is essential for accelerating the transition to low-carbon economies, particularly for emerging and developing countries and plays a key role in these negotiations (Bhandary et al., 2021; Carfora et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2022). Climate objectives involve a financial flow from developed countries to developing ones, alleviating their financial constraints and helping them pursue low-carbon development paths. In this context, it is crucial to assess the environmental efficiency of existing funds to provide scientific evidence and motivate national and international financial institutions to actively participate in mobilizing climate funds.

By using data from 75 recipient countries from 2000 to 2020, our findings suggest that climate finance significantly improves environmental quality by reducing carbon footprint, carbon intensity of GDP, and ecological footprint and improving the environmental performance of the recipient countries. These results underscore the crucial importance of climate funding in combating climate change and promoting sustainable development. The main channels through which climate funds improve environmental quality are energy transition, reforestation and energy efficiency of GDP. Heterogeneity analysis revealed that the effect is driven by mitigation finance and that the financial instrument used in allocating climate funds matters. Funding provided through grants significantly reduces carbon footprint, whereas the effect of funds provided through debt is not significant. Countries with lower debt burden manage climate funds more effectively, utilizing these resources to mitigate the impacts of climate change more significantly. Similarly, countries demonstrating high innovation capacity leverage climate finance, optimizing the use of these funds to enhance their capacity to address environmental challenges. Furthermore, we observe through our results that the level of education matters in the effectiveness of climate funds. Our results suggest that climate funds from China have a weaker effect on greenhouse gas emissions compared to those provided by donors from the Development Assistance Committee (DAC). Furthermore, we highlight a dynamic effect of climate finance, with a persistent impact lasting up to the ninth year. These findings provide empirical evidence that climate finance is a sustainable instrument for improving environmental quality. These findings indicate that the effectiveness of climate fund utilization is significantly influenced by the pre-existing macroeconomic conditions like debt management, social context and structural change potential measure by innovation capacity of recipient countries.

Consistent with our empirical findings, policy recommendations can be formulated for both donor and recipient countries. First, recipient countries should develop a stable macroeconomic framework to better attract climate funds and fully benefit from these funds for sustainable development. Fiscal consolidation and significant innovation investment are indeed prerequisites for enhanced effectiveness of climate funds. Secondly, climate change education program could help to accelerate climate change mitigation¹⁷. These findings highlight that research collaborations that build local capacity can enhance the effectiveness of climate finance, underscoring the importance of initiatives like C3A and the UN's One UN Climate Change

17. Countries like Namibia, Bhutan, and Zambia have already introduced climate change education programs to transform their educational systems into engines of green growth (UNDP, 2023)

Learning Partnership. Thirdly, for donor countries, consistent and substantial financial support would be an effective way to achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement, given the persistent effects of climate finance on environmental quality improvement. Providing finance through grant instrument is more benefit for climate action than debt instrument¹⁸. Redirecting climate finance and conditioning its access on the implementation of climate education systems, technological innovation, and improved debt management could also accelerate climate change mitigation, given the long-term trade-off between environmental debt and public debt¹⁹ (Boly et al., 2022). Including emerging countries in climate action under COP15²⁰ commitments, could not only help to reduce the climate finance gap but also accelerate mitigation efforts

In conclusion, our study supports that climate finance is a powerful lever for improving environmental quality, but its effectiveness depends heavily on the economic and structural context of the recipient countries. However, a possible extension of this study would be to incorporate more comprehensive datasets on climate finance over a longer period, and to use methods such as the Synthetic Control Method to conduct country-by-country analyses, in order to better understand the effect of climate finance on country-specific carbon emission (Ben-Michael et al., 2021).

18. Donor countries should still tailor the financial instruments used in allocating climate funds to the context of each country because no single instrument appears to be right for all countries at all times (Bolton et al., 2023; Bhandary et al., 2021).

19. Based on our findings regarding debt and the environmental efforts of countries, the new financing instrument of the International Monetary Fund, the Resilience and Sustainability Trust, represents a better channel through which developed countries can finance climate action in emerging and developing economies. Indeed, this instrument incorporates a set of economic and environmental reforms as a prerequisite for disbursing climate finance (IFM, 2024). It provides an opportunity to tailor financing conditions to the economic and environmental realities of each country.

20. At COP15 in Copenhagen, developed countries committed to mobilizing \$30 billion in new and additional funds for the 2010–2013 period, under what was termed “fast-start” climate finance. This transitional funding was expected to scale up to \$100 billion per year by 2020 in the form of long-term, structured climate finance (Carfora et al., 2017).

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7 Appendix

7.1 Additional Robustness Checks

In this subsection, we addressed potential distortions from outliers by applying winsorization to our data, setting limits at the 1st and 99th, the 5th and 95th and the 10th and 90th percentiles. Indeed, the effectiveness of an estimator depends on its robustness to outliers. This method then adjusts extreme values, reducing their impact on the overall analysis. Reassessing our models with the adjusted data, we found that our initial results held firm, demonstrating their resilience against the influence of outliers.

Table 10 – *Robustness Test: Winsorisation*

Variable : Carbon Footprint					
	Baseline	1%	5%	10%	BRICS
Climate Finance (log)	-0.051** (0.021)				-0.051*** (0.019)
Climate Finance (log)		-0.051** (0.021)			
Climate Finance (log)			-0.055*** (0.020)		
Climate Finance (log)				-0.059*** (0.022)	
Observations	1141	1141	1141	1141	1069
Country-Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Baseline Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R ²	0.248	0.244	0.293	0.219	0.213
Kleibergen-Paap F-stat	18.948	19.094	19.022	18.003	21.842

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

We also conducted a replication of our analysis excluding the newly industrialized BRICS countries—Brazil, India, China, and South Africa (see 10). Russia was not included in our sample due to the unavailability of data for our key variables. Compared to other developing nations, BRICS countries, feature diverse economies and rapidly growing populations within relatively stable political frameworks. However, to support their swift economic development, they emit substantial amounts of carbon dioxide (Wang et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2022). Additionally, energy consumption trends within BRICS are accelerating, significantly shifting the global energy consumption landscape. The role of BRICS in global economic growth is crucial, and finding a balance between economic advancement and environmental sustainability poses a significant challenge for these nations (Wang et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2022). Excluding these countries from our sample is a way to test the sensitivity of our results because the interest parameter could be drawn by these countries. Excluding BRICS countries also allows us to account for the fact that some donor countries might relocate their polluting activities to developing countries after ratifying environmental treaties.

The persistence of our original findings after winsorization in table 10 underscores their reliability. This robustness check confirms that the relationships identified in our study are stable, not artifacts of extreme data points. By proving that our conclusions withstand such rigorous sensitivity testing, we reinforce the validity of our research and ensure its applicability in a broader context.

Figure 5 – Impulse Response Function Full period

Table 11 – Impulse Response Function

Horizon	IRF	Std. Err.	IRF Low	IRF Up	Significance
0	-0.00523	0.00310	-0.01144	0.00099	Significant
1	-0.00669	0.00353	-0.01377	0.00039	Significant
2	-0.00819	0.00473	-0.01768	0.00129	Significant
3	-0.01100	0.00501	-0.02103	-0.00096	Significant
4	-0.01906	0.00648	-0.03205	-0.00608	Significant
5	-0.01451	0.00525	-0.02504	-0.00398	Significant
6	-0.01076	0.00346	-0.01769	-0.00384	Significant
7	-0.00758	0.00317	-0.01395	-0.00122	Significant
8	-0.00620	0.00342	-0.01305	0.00066	Significant
9	0.00094	0.00578	-0.01065	0.01252	Not Significant
10	-0.00030	0.00451	-0.00934	0.00875	Not Significant
11	0.00308	0.00393	-0.00480	0.01095	Not Significant
12	0.00493	0.00307	-0.00123	0.01108	Not Significant
13	0.00305	0.00403	-0.00504	0.01114	Not Significant
14	0.00490	0.00309	-0.00131	0.01111	Not Significant
15	0.00212	0.00238	-0.00267	0.00690	Not Significant
16	0.00238	0.00270	-0.00303	0.00780	Not Significant
17	-0.00023	0.00168	-0.00360	0.00315	Not Significant
18	0.00251	0.00236	-0.00224	0.00726	Not Significant

7.2 Climate finance data description

Figure 6 – *Physical Vulnerability Index to CC*
 Source: Author calculation, ND GAIN data

Figure 7 – *Carbon Footprint*
 Source: Author calculation, EORA data.

Figure 8 – *Total Climate Finance*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data

Figure 9 – *Adaptation funds*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data.

Figure 10 – *Mitigation funds*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data.

Figure 11 – *Climate Finance repartition by sector*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data.

Figure 12 – *CF repartition by financial instrument*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data.

Figure 13 – *Chinese Climate Finance vs DAC members climate finance*

Figure 14 – *Climate finance allocation by financial instrument-number of project*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data

Figure 15 – *Climate finance allocation by financial instrument-Volume of Finance*
 Source: Author calculation, OECD data.

7.3 Instrumental Variables

Figure 16 – Probability to receive Finance (Prob2) and recipient climate finance

Source: Author Calculation from OECD data.

Figure 17 – Instrumental Variable(IV2) and recipient climate finance

Source: Author Calculation from OECD and IEA data.

Figure 18 – Instrumental Variable(IV3) and recipient climate finance

Source: Author Calculation from OECD and IEA data.

7.4 Descriptive statistic

Table 12 – Descriptive statistics

Variables	Observations	mean	std	min	max
Carbon Footprint per capita(EORA)	1575	3.62	2.96	0.00	18.11
Carbon Footprint per capita(WID)	1554	3.88	3.01	0.04	26.12
Carbon intensity of GDP	1575	1596.69	1644.77	0.00	18809.71
Ecological Footprint	1547	1.96	1.36	0.27	8.68
Environmental performance index	1155	8.75	1.82	4.73	12.87
Total Climate finance	1575	133906.34	391175.99	0.00	6412803.44
Adaptation Finance	1575	46247.57	136839.78	0.00	2042393.09
Mitigation Finance	1575	102573.27	323179.55	0.00	5677721.92
Multilateral Finance	792	274653.48	518664.30	1.86	4595736.86
Debt Instrument	537	11.36	1.78	1.31	15.65
Grant Instrument	1478	9.17	2.08	0.33	13.30
GDP per capita	1575	3619.51	2901.13	263.36	14200.27
Population growth	1575	1.58	1.24	-5.28	11.79
Private Investment	1515	24.80	8.79	1.10	76.78
Public Investment	1411	4.33	3.00	0.36	20.37
Trade openness	1522	74.07	31.96	9.96	220.41
Urbanization rate	1575	0.52	0.20	0.08	0.92
Renewable energy use	1570	38.68	30.24	0.06	96.04
Industrial value added	1567	0.22	0.09	0.03	0.55
Energy intensity	1570	5.34	3.04	1.87	26.91
Access to electricity	1575	0.74	0.31	0.03	1.00
Fossil energy use	1574	63.01	29.97	0.00	100.00
Forest Area	1563	28.09	20.97	0.04	75.50
Foreign Direct Investment	1548	3.98	5.25	-37.17	55.07
Woman share in parliament	1483	18.30	11.36	0.00	63.75
Gini index	1554	0.60	0.07	0.39	0.78
Natural Ressource rent	1554	8.20	11.15	0.00	66.06
Corruption index	1233	2.07	0.65	0.50	5.00
Environmental expenditure	597.00	0.15	0.21	0.00	1.17
Debt Burden	1024	10.63	8.88	0.00	53.57
ODA	1549	4.28	5.84	-0.64	48.55
Net rate primary school	999	87.13	12.76	26.83	99.89
Net rate secondary school	698	61.53	23.95	3.28	99.84
Net rate tertiary school	1235	28.09	21.64	0.64	118.88
Patent Application	1,428	18.35	67.95	0	993
Treat	1575	583.57	27.71	509.28	732.02
Treat2	1575	204.74	24.77	125.94	330.66
Prob1	1575	0.34	0.10	0.11	0.55
Prob2	1575	0.21	0.13	0.02	0.56
IV	1575	197.35	63.49	54.56	349.97
IV2	1575	122.45	74.89	9.07	354.55
IV3	1575	69.30	23.90	18.73	146.16

Table 13 – Correlation matrix of the main variables.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)
(1)Carbon Footprint	1.00	0.89	0.09	0.66	-0.08	0.66	-0.30	0.02	0.09	0.18	0.47	-0.56	0.30	0.00	0.44	0.21
(2)Carbon Footprint(WID)	0.89	1.00	0.01	0.77	-0.08	0.63	-0.31	0.09	0.09	0.26	0.52	-0.60	0.31	0.02	0.49	0.29
(3)Carbon intensity of GDP	0.09	0.01	1.00	0.01	-0.14	-0.34	0.08	-0.07	-0.05	-0.00	-0.32	0.15	0.00	0.59	-0.25	-0.03
(4)Ecological Footprint	0.66	0.77	0.01	1.00	-0.10	0.54	-0.30	0.09	0.04	0.21	0.43	-0.41	0.32	0.11	0.36	0.16
(5)Climate Finance	-0.08	-0.08	-0.14	-0.10	1.00	-0.03	-0.04	0.11	0.09	-0.18	-0.06	-0.06	0.01	-0.08	0.11	0.03
(6)GDP per capita	0.66	0.63	-0.34	0.54	-0.03	1.00	-0.33	-0.07	0.07	0.08	0.72	-0.60	0.27	-0.32	0.57	0.14
(7)Population growth	-0.30	-0.31	0.08	-0.30	-0.04	-0.33	1.00	-0.04	0.13	-0.18	-0.29	0.45	0.03	0.08	-0.58	-0.01
(8)private investment	0.02	0.09	-0.07	0.09	0.11	-0.07	-0.04	1.00	0.38	0.21	-0.00	-0.07	0.11	0.18	0.10	0.04
(9)Public investment	0.09	0.09	-0.05	0.04	0.09	0.07	0.13	0.38	1.00	0.15	-0.02	-0.08	0.37	0.07	0.01	0.10
(10)Trade openness	0.18	0.26	-0.00	0.21	-0.18	0.08	-0.18	0.21	0.15	1.00	0.17	-0.28	0.28	-0.02	0.25	0.16
(11)Urbanization	0.47	0.52	-0.32	0.43	-0.06	0.72	-0.29	-0.00	-0.02	0.17	1.00	-0.72	0.27	-0.32	0.67	0.21
(12)Renewable energy	-0.56	-0.60	0.15	-0.41	-0.06	-0.60	0.45	-0.07	-0.08	-0.28	-0.72	1.00	-0.37	0.21	-0.80	-0.45
(13)Industry value added	0.30	0.31	0.00	0.32	0.01	0.27	0.03	0.11	0.37	0.28	0.27	-0.37	1.00	0.02	0.24	0.26
(14)Energy Intensity	0.00	0.02	0.59	0.11	-0.08	-0.32	0.08	0.18	0.07	-0.02	-0.32	0.21	0.02	1.00	-0.27	-0.03
(15) Access to electricity	0.44	0.49	-0.25	0.36	0.11	0.57	-0.58	0.10	0.01	0.25	0.67	-0.80	0.24	-0.27	1.00	0.17
(16)Fossil energy	0.21	0.29	-0.03	0.16	0.03	0.14	-0.01	0.04	0.10	0.16	0.21	-0.45	0.26	-0.03	0.17	1.00

Table 14 – Correlation matrix of the additional variables

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)
(1) Forest Erea	1.00	0.11	0.06	0.28	-0.17	0.18	-0.06	0.06	-0.10	0.05	0.21	0.13	0.20	0.13	0.11	-0.08	-0.05
(2) FDI	0.11	1.00	-0.04	-0.04	0.07	-0.03	-0.09	-0.03	0.04	-0.07	-0.08	-0.01	-0.08	-0.01	0.11	0.06	0.06
(3) Woman share	0.06	-0.04	1.00	0.17	-0.07	0.04	0.04	-0.17	0.12	0.16	0.22	0.17	0.24	0.18	0.15	-0.00	0.01
(4) Gini index	0.28	-0.04	0.17	1.00	-0.04	0.23	-0.02	0.17	0.03	0.20	0.26	0.03	0.28	0.04	0.00	-0.27	-0.32
(5) Natural Ressource rent	-0.17	0.07	-0.07	-0.04	1.00	-0.23	-0.02	-0.14	0.10	0.01	-0.30	-0.26	-0.29	-0.26	-0.10	-0.25	-0.20
(6) Corruption Index	0.18	-0.03	0.04	0.23	-0.23	1.00	0.11	-0.04	-0.01	0.06	0.18	0.07	0.18	0.07	0.19	0.05	0.03
(7) Environmental expense	-0.06	-0.09	0.04	-0.02	-0.02	0.11	1.00	-0.15	-0.08	-0.08	0.03	0.10	0.03	0.10	0.18	0.04	0.03
(8) Debt Burden	0.06	-0.03	-0.17	0.17	-0.14	-0.04	-0.15	1.00	-0.19	0.10	0.10	0.03	0.11	0.04	0.02	-0.08	-0.08
(9) ODA	-0.10	0.04	0.12	0.03	0.10	-0.01	-0.08	-0.19	1.00	-0.07	0.07	0.11	0.06	0.10	-0.38	-0.45	-0.37
(10) Environmental treaties	0.05	-0.07	0.16	0.20	0.01	0.06	-0.08	0.10	-0.07	1.00	0.18	0.03	0.31	0.10	-0.08	-0.13	-0.11
(11) Probability	0.21	-0.08	0.22	0.26	-0.30	0.18	0.03	0.10	0.07	0.18	1.00	0.82	0.99	0.83	-0.09	-0.37	-0.28
(12) Probability 2	0.13	-0.01	0.17	0.03	-0.26	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.11	0.03	0.82	1.00	0.79	1.00	-0.13	-0.26	-0.19
(13) IV	0.20	-0.08	0.24	0.28	-0.29	0.18	0.03	0.11	0.06	0.31	0.99	0.79	1.00	0.81	-0.09	-0.37	-0.28
(14) IV	0.13	-0.01	0.18	0.04	-0.26	0.07	0.10	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.83	1.00	0.81	1.00	-0.13	-0.27	-0.19
(15) Net rate primary school	0.11	0.11	0.15	0.00	-0.10	0.19	0.18	0.02	-0.38	-0.08	-0.09	-0.13	-0.09	-0.13	1.00	0.68	0.48
(16) Net rate secondary school	-0.08	0.06	-0.00	-0.27	-0.25	0.05	0.04	-0.08	-0.45	-0.13	-0.37	-0.26	-0.37	-0.27	0.68	1.00	0.78
(17) Net rate tertiary school	-0.05	0.06	0.01	-0.32	-0.20	0.03	0.03	-0.08	-0.37	-0.11	-0.28	-0.19	-0.28	-0.19	0.48	0.78	1.00

Table 15 – *Stationarity test of climate finance and carbon footprint data*

Variables	Test climate Finance (CF)	Carbon Footprint(CFP)	P-value CF	P-value CFP	
Inverse chi-squared	P	547.6495	207.8550	0.0000	0.0006
Inverse normal	Z	-13.5563	-3.7377	0.0000	0.0001
Inverse logit t	L*	-16.3717	-3.8204	0.0000	0.0001
Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	22.9583	3.6198	0.0000	0.0001

7.5 List of countries

Recipient Countries

Albania, Algeria, Angola, Argentina, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bangladesh, Belarus, Bhutan, Bolivia, Botswana, Brazil, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cabo Verde, Cambodia, China, Colombia, Congo, Costa Rica, Côte d'Ivoire, Dominican Republic, Egypt, El Salvador, Fiji, Georgia, Ghana, Guatemala, Guinea, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Iraq, Jamaica, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Lebanon, Libya, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mali, Mauritius, Mexico, Mongolia, Montenegro, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nepal, Nicaragua, Niger, Nigeria, Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Republic of Moldova, Rwanda, Senegal, Serbia, Sierra Leone, South Africa, State of Palestine, Sudan, Tajikistan, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Uganda, Ukraine, United Republic of Tanzania, Uzbekistan.

Donor Countries

Australia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Canada, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, United States.

7.6 Source of data

Table 16 – Source of data

Variables	Definition	Measure	Source
Carbon footprint	Consumption-based accounting (CBA) of emissions (also called carbon footprints) accounts for emissions associated with imported and exported goods. CBA reports the total emissions associated with final demand in each country.	GgCO ₂ eq	EORA, WID
Carbon intensity of GDP	Carbon intensity is the ratio of carbon emission to gross domestic product.	GgCO ₂ eq per billion US dollar	EORA
Ecological Footprint	Ecological Footprint accounting measures the demand on and supply of nature.	global hectares	Global Footprint Network
Climate Finance	climate finance includes climate-related development finance from bilateral, multilateral and private philanthropic sources including both concessional and non-concessional activities .	constant 2021 US\$	EOCD, CRS
GDP per capita	GDP per capita is gross domestic product divided by midyear population. GDP is the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included in the value of the products. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation of fabricated assets or for depletion and degradation of natural resources.	constant 2015 US\$	WDI
Demographic Growth	Annual population growth rate for year t is the exponential rate of growth of midyear population from year t-1 to t, expressed as a percentage . Population is based on the de facto definition of population, which counts all residents regardless of legal status or citizenship	Annual Percentage	WDI
Private Investment	Private capital stock (constructed based on private investment flows), in billions of constant 2017 international dollars.	constant 2017 international dollars	IMF
Public Investment	General government investment (gross fixed capital formation), in billions of constant 2017 international dollars.	constant 2017 international dollars	IMF
Trade openness	Trade is the sum of exports and imports of goods and services measured as a share of gross domestic product.	Percentage of GDP	WDI
Urbanization Rate	Urban population refers to people living in urban areas as defined by national statistical offices. The data are collected and smoothed by United Nations Population Division.	Percentage of the total population.	WDI
Renewable energy Consumption	Renewable energy consumption is the share of renewables energy in total final energy consumption.	Percentage of total final energy consumption	WDI

Variables	Definition	Measure	Source
Industry value added	Industry (including construction) corresponds to ISIC divisions 05-43 and includes manufacturing (ISIC divisions 10-33). It comprises value added in mining, manufacturing (also reported as a separate subgroup), construction, electricity, water, and gas. Value added is the net output of a sector after adding up all outputs and subtracting intermediate inputs. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation of fabricated assets or depletion and degradation of natural resources. The origin of value added is determined by the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC), revision 4. Note: For VAB countries, gross value added at factor cost is used as the denominator.	constant 2015 US\$	UNIDO
Energy intensity	Energy intensity level of primary energy is the ratio between energy supply and gross domestic product measured at purchasing power parity. Energy intensity is an indication of how much energy is used to produce one unit of economic output. Lower ratio indicates that less energy is used to produce one unit of output.	MJ/\$2017 PPP GDP	WDI
Access to electricity	Access to electricity is the percentage of population with access to electricity. Electrification data are collected from industry, national surveys and international sources.	% of population	WDI
Fossil fuel energy consumption	Fossil fuel comprises coal, oil, petroleum, and natural gas products.	% of total	WDI
Forest Area	Forest area is land under natural or planted stands of trees of at least 5 meters in situ, whether productive or not, and excludes tree stands in agricultural production systems (for example, in fruit plantations and agroforestry systems) and trees in urban parks and gardens.	% of land area	WDI
FDI	Foreign direct investment (FDI) refers to net inflows of investment to acquire a lasting management interest (10 percent or more of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in an economy other than that of the investor. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, other long-term capital, and short-term capital as shown in the balance of payments. This series shows net inflows (new investment inflows less disinvestment) in the reporting economy from foreign investors and is divided by GDP.	% du PIB	WDI
Woman share in Parliament	Women in parliaments are the percentage of parliamentary seats in a single or lower chamber held by women.	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	WDI
Natural Ressources	Total natural resources rents are the sum of oil rents, natural gas rents, coal rents (hard and soft), mineral rents, and forest rents.	%of GDP	WDI

Variables	Definition	Measure	Source
Gini index	Gini index measures the extent to which the distribution of income (or, in some cases, consumption expenditure) among individuals or households within an economy deviates from a perfectly equal distribution. A Lorenz curve plots the cumulative percentages of total income received against the cumulative number of recipients, starting with the poorest individual or household. The Gini index measures the area between the Lorenz curve and a hypothetical line of absolute equality, expressed as a percentage of the maximum area under the line. Thus a Gini index of 0 represents perfect equality, while an index of 100 implies perfect inequality.		WDI
Corruption index	Control of Corruption captures perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as “capture” of the state by elites and private interests. Standard error indicates the precision of the estimate of governance. Larger values of the standard error indicate less precise estimates.		ICRG
Patents Applications	Residents Patent applications	% Numbers of application	WIPO
Environmental Expenditure	Government expenditures on a specified set of activities including pollution abatement, protection of biodiversity landscape, waste and wastewater management, within the framework of the Classification of Functions of Government (COFOG).	%of GDP	IFM
Environmental treaty	List of environmental treaties ratified by countries from 1815 to 2015		IEA
Renewable Energy generation	RE share of electricity generation (%)	%of total energy	IRENA